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Chair: _____

**Examining the Spectrum of Community Development Approaches:
A Typology of Community Development Models.**

A thesis submitted to

The University of Cincinnati

in partial fulfillment of the
requirements for the degree of

MASTER OF COMMUNITY PLANNING

School of Planning
College of Design, Architecture, Art, and Planning

May 22, 2006

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B.S. Human and Organizational Development, Vanderbilt University, 2003.

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Abstract

This thesis examines models of community development in order to determine the areas in which they are most effective at impacting communities. Community development researchers and practitioners often ignore the wide range of possible approaches to community development by choosing to focus on a particular model. This thesis broadens the perspective of community development literature by focusing on the wide range of possible approaches and the specific aspects of community development in which each is most successful. To accomplish this task, five models are selected, organized based on levels of community participation, and examined in regard to their ability to impact communities based on a systematic evaluation framework. The result is a typology of community development models that highlights the differences between different models of community development and identifies the aspects of community development to which each is uniquely well suited.

Acknowledgements

I want to thank first and foremost my committee, particularly Dr. Romanos, for all the time and thought they put into making this all that it could be. This thesis would not be what it is today without your ideas and support. I also want to thank my family for their constant support and my friends for still being there even though I have not seen them for weeks while working on this paper. Finally, I want to thank Andrea. I do not know where I would be without your encouragement.

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	2
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	9
CHAPTER 1: Introduction	10
1.1 Problem Statement	10
1.2 Purpose of the Study	11
1.3 Outline of Thesis	12
CHAPTER 2: Literature Review	13
2.1 Terminology:	13
2.1.1 Neighborhood.....	13
2.1.2 Community.....	14
2.1.3 Community Development.....	15
2.2 Examination of Past Typologies	17
2.3 Evaluation Framework	19
CHAPTER 3: Methodology	28
3.1 Identification of the Main Models	28
3.2 Development of an Organizational Framework	29
3.3 Examination and Evaluation of the Models	30
3.4 Completion of Case Studies	30
3.5 Summary	31
CHAPTER 4: Typology of Community Development Models	32
4.1 Community Organizing	33
4.1.1 History.....	33
4.1.2 Structure.....	35
4.1.3 Effectiveness.....	38
4.1.3.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	38
4.1.3.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	39
4.1.3.3 <i>Image</i>	39
4.1.3.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	40
4.1.4 Conclusions.....	41
4.2 Community Development Corporations	42
4.2.1 History.....	43
4.2.2 Structure.....	44

4.2.3 Effectiveness.....	46
4.2.3.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	47
4.2.3.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	47
4.2.3.3 <i>Image</i>	48
4.2.3.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	48
4.2.4 Conclusions.....	49
4.3 Comprehensive Community Initiatives	50
4.3.1 History.....	50
4.3.2 Structure.....	52
4.3.3 Effectiveness.....	54
4.3.3.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	55
4.3.3.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	55
4.3.3.3 <i>Image</i>	56
4.3.3.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	57
4.3.4 Conclusions.....	58
4.4 Local Government	58
4.4.1 History.....	58
4.4.2 Structure.....	62
4.4.3 Effectiveness.....	65
4.4.3.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	65
4.4.3.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	66
4.4.3.3 <i>Image</i>	66
4.4.3.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	67
4.4.4 Conclusions.....	67
4.5 Business Leadership Coalitions	68
4.5.1 History.....	69
4.5.2 Structure.....	71
4.5.3 Effectiveness.....	73
4.5.3.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	73
4.5.3.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	74
4.5.3.3 <i>Image</i>	74
4.5.3.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	75
4.5.4 Conclusions.....	75
 CHAPTER 5: Illustrative Examples	 77
5.1 Price Hill Will	77
5.1.1 History and Structure.....	78
5.1.1.1 <i>Neighborhood Background</i>	78
5.1.1.2 <i>Organization History</i>	79
5.1.1.3 <i>Structure</i>	80
5.1.2 Outcomes.....	82
5.1.2.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	82
5.1.2.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	83
5.1.2.3 <i>Image</i>	84

5.1.2.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	84
5.1.3 Conclusions.....	85
5.2 Lincoln Heights Community Improvement Corporation	86
5.2.1 History and Structure.....	87
5.2.1.1 <i>Neighborhood Background</i>	87
5.2.1.2 <i>Organization History</i>	87
5.2.1.3 <i>Structure</i>	88
5.2.2 Outcomes.....	90
5.2.2.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	90
5.2.2.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	91
5.2.2.3 <i>Image</i>	92
5.2.2.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	93
5.2.3 Conclusions.....	93
5.3 Brighton Center	94
5.3.1 History and Structure.....	94
5.3.1.1 <i>Neighborhood Background</i>	94
5.3.1.2 <i>Organization History</i>	95
5.3.1.3 <i>Structure</i>	96
5.3.2 Outcomes.....	98
5.3.2.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	98
5.3.2.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	99
5.3.2.3 <i>Image</i>	100
5.3.2.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	100
5.3.3 Conclusions.....	101
5.4 City of Cincinnati	102
5.4.1 History and Structure.....	102
5.4.1.1 <i>Neighborhood Background</i>	102
5.4.1.2 <i>Organization History</i>	103
5.4.1.3 <i>Structure</i>	104
5.4.2 Outcomes.....	109
5.4.2.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	109
5.4.2.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	110
5.4.2.3 <i>Image</i>	111
5.4.2.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	111
5.4.3 Conclusions.....	112
5.5 Cincinnati Center City Development Corporation	112
5.5.1 History and Structure.....	113
5.5.1.1 <i>Neighborhood Background</i>	113
5.5.1.2 <i>Organization History</i>	114
5.5.1.3 <i>Structure</i>	114
5.5.2 Outcomes.....	116
5.5.2.1 <i>Physical Conditions</i>	117
5.5.2.2 <i>Market Conditions</i>	118
5.5.2.3 <i>Image</i>	118

5.5.2.4 <i>Neighborhood Management</i>	199
5.5.3 Conclusions.....	120
CHAPTER 6: Findings	121
6.1 Introduction to Findings	121
6.2 Evaluation of the Models' Effectiveness	122
6.2.1 Physical Conditions.....	122
6.2.2 Market Conditions.....	123
6.2.3 Image.....	124
6.2.4 Neighborhood Management.....	125
6.3 Evaluation of Findings	127
6.4 Suggestions for Future Research	129
BIBLIOGRAPHY	131

List of Figures

Figure 1: Typology and Illustrative Example Overview.....	32
Figure 2: Department of Community Development and Planning Organizational Chart.....	105
Figure 3: DCDP Development Opportunity Teams.....	107
Figure 4: 3CDC Organizational Chart.....	106
Figure 5: Community Development Models' Areas of Effectiveness.....	126

CHAPTER 1: Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

Many communities throughout the United States, particularly in urban areas, are affected by numerous serious problems. Cities, which were in many cases built during the industrial revolution, have faced significant out-migration primarily spurred by shifting patterns of employment and ill-conceived federal policies. Concentrated poverty, lack of jobs, crime, lack of adequate housing, are just a few of the many issues facing urban neighborhoods throughout the country that have been largely driven by these factors (Jargowski 1998, Wilson 1996). The large number and complicated nature of the problems facing these communities result in a wide variety of proposed solutions. While there is general agreement that these problems exist, there is little consensus on how these problems should be addressed. Therefore, different communities and different organizations within communities utilize a wide variety of approaches designed to address urban problems. That is to say, goals and methods for community improvement differ based on how one views urban problems and what constitutes solutions to these problems. However, these approaches all fall under the banner of what is termed “community development”.

Despite the differences that exist among approaches, those who are involved in what is known as community development often take these differences for granted and concentrate on a narrow spectrum of approaches based on their own personal opinions or experiences. Consequently, these various approaches are often viewed in isolation and are adopted based on ideology and other factors rather than how they address the goals most relevant to a particular community. The fact that diversity exist among the various

models and approaches, the failure to recognize these differences, and the lack of clarity about how particular methods function in relation to one another leads to the question, “What are the main models or approaches to community development and in what dimensions of community improvement is each model most effective?”

1.2 Purpose of the Study

Understanding the differences between models of community development will enable those in the field to have a basis from which to analyze their efforts more objectively. The purpose of this thesis is to develop a typology that will examine the main models of community development, their origins, general structure, and the areas of community development in which they are most effective. Past research and illustrative examples will be used to identify and analyze the structure and outcomes of each of the main models of community development in order to organize a typology that provides a framework for comparing community development models across the wide spectrum that exists. Such a typology is very different from the typical narrow view most people have of community development that takes into account only one or two possible approaches and ignores other possible approaches.

Developing a typology that covers all of the various approaches to community development serves as a tool for both researchers and practitioners. The typology enables community development researchers and practitioners, along with community residents, to evaluate existing or proposed strategies in regard to how well they align with the needs and goals of the community they are attempting to improve. The end product is a tool to assist those engaging in community development and that allows those individuals and

groups to take a step back from their work to analyze their own models. Doing so makes it possible for individuals and groups to realize the limitations of each particular model, discover opportunities to be more effective based on the strengths of their model, and can help them think about possibilities for adapting their model or partnering with other organizations to address more effectively the needs of the communities they are working to develop. At the very least, the typology can serve as a starting point to get practitioners to think more broadly about what community development can be and to keep an open mind about different approaches to solving community problems.

1.3 Outline of Thesis

As stated previously, the purpose of this thesis is to create a typology that identifies the primary models of community development and analyzes their effectiveness at addressing a range of aspects of community improvement. However, before delving into the typology itself, it is necessary to address previous research in this area and highlights the shortcomings within the literature this thesis intends to address. This is undertaken in the literature review in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 follows with an explanation of the methodology used in developing the typology. Next, Chapter 4 develops the typology and Chapter 5 contains the illustrative examples that provide real world examples of and evidence for the conclusions reached based on the literature in the typology. Finally Chapter 6 summarizes the findings of the research and offers suggestions for future research.

CHAPTER 2: Literature Review

2.1 Terminology

Before developing a typology, it is necessary to introduce and define certain terms which are relevant to the discussion of community improvement strategies. For example, attempts to address urban problems at a neighborhood generally fit under the generic term community development (community development can also refer to efforts to improve rural areas, but the focus of this study is efforts in and around urban areas). Examining the meaning of the term community development is important to understanding the context of this discussion, but before doing so it is worthwhile to briefly discuss what is meant by the term “community” and the related term “neighborhood”, as well as how these terms relate to one another. While there is general consensus among those interested in community development that the neighborhood or community level is the best setting to begin any attempt to address urban problems (Peterman 2000, 10), it is not always clear to what the terms “neighborhood” and “community” refer.

2.1.1 Neighborhood

In recent history, planners’ and other interested parties’ understanding of the terms has shifted. Beginning in the early 20th century, the term “neighborhood” was often used to describe “urban villages” that were separated in some way from the larger urban area (Peterman 2000, 13). This concept was influenced by the garden city model originally conceived by Ebenezer Howard (Southworth and Ben-Joseph 1995, 70). Over time this idea was enhanced by further suburbanization, as neighborhoods were seen as

places that could be used to block the intrusion of the unwanted problems of the city at large (Langdon 1994, 47). However, this definition of neighborhood is limiting and does not adequately address the complex nature of individual neighborhoods and the wide variations between different neighborhoods. In addition, there are urban areas that do not fit into this definition that are nevertheless widely referred to as neighborhoods. Gans (1991) offers a different perspective, focusing on the links between individuals and their ability to self-govern as the primary determinates for defining a neighborhood. Self-governing is not limited to participation in official government. Self-governing, as Gans refers to it, is also meant to include activities encompassing the regulation of social norms and other similar activities. Therefore, a neighborhood is a geographic area in which individual residents come together to collectively self-govern.

2.1.2 Community

This definition of a neighborhood, based on geographic constraints and the ability to self-govern, will be used for the remainder of this paper. Defined in this way, the term neighborhood is very similar to the term “community”. Community generally refers to a group of individuals who have something in common and is typically used to refer to a group of individuals who have some type of interaction related to self government (Peterman 2000). However, although neighborhoods are seen as explicitly geographically based, communities are not necessarily limited in this way. For example, one can belong to a church community that extends throughout a city or even across the country. However, in this discussion of community development, the term community will be assumed to have a geographic component and therefore can be used

interchangeably with neighborhood for the purposes of this discussion. Both terms will be used to refer to a geographic area where local residents have some tie to one another and some ability to self-govern.

2.1.3 Community Development

Now that the term community and the related term neighborhood are understood, the term “community development” can be examined. Community development can be defined in a number of ways, each very different from the other. Yet, unlike the terms community and neighborhood, it is not necessary for this discussion to nail down an exact definition of what the term means. In fact, the differences in meaning given to the term community development highlight the differences in the approaches that are the focus of this analysis. It is important to remember that it is not the different definitions of community development that determine the strategies implemented but rather the reverse. Looking into the differences in meaning applied to the term illustrates the wide range of approaches to solving community issues that fall under the banner of community development. At its most basic, the term community development can be used very generally (as in the title of this work) to refer to any efforts to improve a particular community or communities. Community development is “an action that is purposively directed towards altering local conditions in a positive way” (Wilkinson 1991, 8).

However, more often than not those using the term are referring to a specific type of community development. For example, the term is often used to refer specifically to social or relational development (Summers 1986). Used in this manner, community development refers to actions which seek to build social capital, promote interaction, and

empower community residents to affect conditions in their community (Vidal 1998, 14). On the other hand, community development can also refer to efforts to improve the economic or structural conditions of a community (Bridger and Luloff 2003). Such efforts may focus on business or job creation and physical development. These two uses of the same term refer to very different actions. These differences in the use of the term highlight the differences in opinion about how to solve community problems that exist between those using the term in one sense and those using it in another. These differences in turn lead to the development of different models for solving community problems. Both definitions and the efforts that fall under them fit under the overall banner of community development as well, but little is done to sort out or clarify the differences in the various approaches.

The sharp contrast between these two uses of the term is usually only delineated by the context in which the term is used, as its exact meaning is rarely explicitly stated. This leads to those who focus on the social aspect of community development developing very different strategies and employing very different models from those who focus on the economic aspects of community development, but both continue to be referred to as community development, without clear distinctions being made about how the strategies and goals of each approach differ from the others. This discussion of the definition of community development is highly simplified and is not meant to illustrate all of the different meanings individuals and groups attribute to the term. The term is often used to refer to a number of other specific approaches to community development. The explanation of these two particular uses of the term is merely used to highlight the wide

range of efforts that are ascribed to the term community development and the lack of research, knowledge or thought about the differences that exist among them.

2.2 Examination of Past Typologies

Despite the wide variety of approaches and the differences in their intended outcomes, very little if any literature on community development addresses these distinctions. Almost all the literature on the subject focuses on a single model or a small range of related models while ignoring other possible approaches (Gittell and Vidal 1998). Little or no attention has been given to developing or analyzing any type of comprehensive typology of community development approaches. For example, in their discussion of community development models Thomas and Grigsby (2000) identify only two models, efforts that develop from within the community which are led by community members and efforts that are instigated and run by professionals from outside the community. Although this is a useful distinction and this distinction goes further towards acknowledging the differences between community development approaches than most other literature, this typology is far too simple to allow meaningful comparisons of specific community development efforts.

In one of the only pieces of research that addresses the development of a truly comprehensive typology, Lane and Dorfman (1997) created five different means of organizing community development approaches into a typology by borrowing and expanding upon five typologies created or suggested by others. The authors propose that typologies can be created based on five factors: level of community involvement, power

structure, partnership structure, change agent/organization relationship, and goal orientation.

The factors identified by the authors are useful ways for thinking about how to organize the wide range of community development approaches into a framework in which they can be effectively analyzed by allowing for some meaningful comparison across the continuum. However, in their analysis the authors, like most other authors in the field, are strictly focused on approaches that attempt to build social capital, rather than taking into account the entire range of models that could be utilized to attempt to improve conditions within a community. Despite creating several meaningful frameworks which can be used to develop a comprehensive typology, Lane and Dorfman's work suffers from the same shortcoming of most community development literature. It is too narrowly focused and therefore misses many possible approaches to improving communities. The typologies these authors develop do not help the reader think more broadly about different efforts to improve community. Like most others in the field, without explicitly saying so, Lane and Dorfman have already made a decision about what type of model is the most effective before critically examining the evidence provided by the entire range of models and therefore create typologies that are lacking critical information that could be used to think more broadly about what successful community development is.

In addition, Lane and Dorfman do not theoretically or empirically analyze approaches based on their typologies but rather describe the various approaches (in regard to how they relate to social capital) across the continuums they have set up and simply suggest which is best. There has been no attempt to investigate systematically the

various models and determine how they relate to one another and the areas in which each is effective. Furthermore, the lack of exploration into areas of effectiveness ignores differences in needs across communities and suggests that there is one best practice for all neighborhoods. Lane and Dorfman do provide a valuable tool for thinking about ways to organize a typology of community development approaches. However, their use of those tools is extremely limited, ignoring many of the models and many of the different situations communities are faced with. The goal of this thesis is to taking these next steps to develop a comprehensive typology that incorporates analysis of the effectiveness of each of the approaches to allow communities to examine which approach or combination of approach is a best fit for their unique needs.

2.3 Evaluation Framework

Before a discussion of the theoretical effectiveness of each of the various models in influencing separate areas of community improvement can be conducted it is necessary to define the relevant areas of community improvement that serve as the framework for this discussion. A uniform framework is necessary in order to make comparisons between models that all aim generally to improve communities but can vary in regard to what their goals are and what they view as community improvement. In order to overcome these differences it is necessary to develop a standard for what is considered a successful community. In other words, the attributes of a successful community must be defined in order to evaluate and compare conflicting efforts to improve communities.

Although defining the attributes of a successful community might seem basic, there have not been many attempts to do so systematically. Most definitions of what

makes a community successful are narrowly focused. Similar to the definitions of community development discussed previously, definitions of successful communities are typically focused on attributes related to particular areas of interest, rather than the many dimensions that comprise successful community. In addition, authors who attempt to develop comprehensive definitions often highlight very general attributes that are difficult to clearly and easily measure. For example, Thomas and Grigsby (2000) highlight three characteristics of “good communities”: sustainability, safety, and self-determination. However, there is no mention of specific measures or outcomes that can be used to evaluate communities based on these characteristics. Such a definition is not very useful for attempting a systematic evaluation of community development efforts.

On the other hand, Nedland and Schubert (2002) offer a somewhat unique perspective for defining successful neighborhoods that fits well with the broad range of models, goals, and outcomes examined in this paper and goes into more depth in an attempt to identify the attributes that make a community successful. To begin with, they define a successful neighborhood as one in which it makes economic sense for people to invest their time, money and energy, as well as one in which neighbors successfully manage relationships with one another (Nedland and Schubert 2002, 28). Stated more simply, successful neighborhoods are those in which, given the opportunity, people would choose to live, or, to use their terminology, neighborhoods of choice.

Fortunately, the authors do not stop there. In order to take into account the different dimensions in which a community can be improved, Nedland and Schubert (2002) identify four main factors that contribute to a neighborhood becoming a neighborhood of choice. The first is a neighborhood’s *image*. A positive image and

outlook for the future attracts investment in both time and money, a key sign of a neighborhood of choice. The next factor they identify is the health of the economic *market*, both for commercial and residential property. This is related to, but not the same as, a neighborhood's image. A positive image can be a factor reflected in a healthy real estate market but other factors can contribute as well. The key is for property values to be stable or increasing, therefore allowing people to make sound investments in the neighborhood. The third factor is the *physical condition* of the neighborhood, its buildings and infrastructure. The physical condition of a neighborhood not only affects the neighborhood's image and the real estate market but has an impact of public infrastructure as well. Together these aspects of a neighborhood's physical condition have an effect on a neighborhood's status as a neighborhood of choice. The last factor the authors identify is *neighborhood management*. The term neighborhood management refers to the capacity of local residents to affect both their own lives and the conditions of their surroundings. In discussing neighborhood management the authors note that

“collective action by residents, institutions, and businesses will ensure neighborhoods will compete well with other neighborhoods for resources. Residents will have the capacity to manage the day-to-day activities on their blocks. Neighbors will feel comfortable looking out for each other, getting together to work on problems, taking action to reinforce positive standards and actions, etc. Neighbors will feel safe in the neighborhood.” (Howell, Nedland, and Schubert 2002, 6)

Positive changes in each of these areas contribute to a community becoming a neighborhood of choice and they constitute good measures of success for community development initiatives.

The neighborhoods of choice concept provides a solid, balanced framework for beginning to analyze community development models. However, even this definition of

successful communities does not go far enough to allow for a systematic comparison of community development efforts. In order to make effective comparisons across different models it is necessary to define more clearly what is meant by each of the four concepts as advanced by its proponents. For example, neighborhood image is how people think of the neighborhood. However, upon closer examination it is not clear exactly what “people” are being referred to. To clarify that issue, it is necessary to distinguish two distinct types of neighborhood image, both what neighborhood residents think about the neighborhood and how people outside the neighborhood view it. This is important because these opinions could be different and can have very different effects on the neighborhood’s improvement. Positive image within the neighborhood can lead to efforts from local citizens to improve or maintain conditions in the neighborhood while a positive image from the outside could help to spark outside investment into the neighborhood. In both cases a positive neighborhood image is ideal, but each can lead to very different neighborhood outcomes. Similarly, differing views from outside and inside a neighborhood can lead to even more distinct outcomes. For these reasons it is important to distinguish between image as seen by people inside a community and image as seen by those outside the community.

Likewise, it is important to breakdown the other three areas highlighted by the neighborhoods of choice framework. Of these, a neighborhood’s market condition is the easiest to clarify. A neighborhood’s market can reasonably be broken down into the market for residential real estate and the market for commercial real estate. Both markets are important to a neighborhood’s overall success but again, each can have different effects on the community. As discussed earlier, the goal is stable or steadily increasing

property values within each market. A neighborhood with increasing residential property values and decreasing commercial real estate property values will encounter a unique set of issues and will require a unique set of interventions to correct those issues, as will a neighborhood in the reverse situation. Likewise, a neighborhood with declining property values in both areas will require a more comprehensive approach to improving neighborhood conditions. Because of these differences, it is important to separate the commercial and residential real estate markets in discussing each of the community development models.

Neighborhood image and market condition, although very complicated concepts, can be unpacked rather easily for the purposes of this discussion. Although whole books could be and have been written on either subject, they can be left relatively general and still remain useful in comparing community development models. Without delving too deeply into all the aspects that could play into a neighborhood's image, it is sufficient to limit the discussion to whether or not the neighborhood's image is seen as positive in the identified groups. Likewise, real estate markets are extremely complicated and a thorough discussion of them is beyond the capacity or goal of this discussion. However, stable and increasing property values in the two identified markets are a sufficient indicator of the overall health of the market and are directly related to willingness to invest in the community.

However, the remaining two concepts are not so easily clarified. Both involve multiple aspects and do not lend themselves to a simple, clear-cut indicator for evaluation in the same way the previous two concepts do. The first of these concepts is the physical condition of the neighborhood. Again at first glance this may appear relatively simple.

Yet, upon a closer look it becomes clear that simply lumping a broad range of things into the generic concept of physical conditions is not sufficient when it comes to critically evaluating the differences between outcomes for different community development models. Many things labeled as representing the physical conditions of the neighborhood could easily mask real differences in outcomes across the models being examined. Because of this, it is necessary to clarify exactly what constitutes the physical condition of the community in order to better serve the purposes of this study. A neighborhood's physical conditions will be broken down into three areas, condition of building stock (including both residential homes and commercial buildings), environmental conditions, and condition of the neighborhood's infrastructure.

However, even these three concepts must be further defined if specific examples are to be compared. Building stock refers to the physical state of homes and businesses in the community. This includes age of the buildings, level of upkeep and maintenance, and amount of redevelopment or new construction. The environmental condition of the neighborhood refers to the amount and condition of greenspace, the presence of heavy industry and other potential pollutants, and the cleanliness of the community. In this study a neighborhood's infrastructure includes the condition of local roads and sidewalks, schools and other government buildings, and parks and other public spaces. Examining a neighborhood based on these general requirements is not as detailed as possible but once again is suitable for the broad nature of this study.

The last concept that must be further refined is perhaps the most difficult to simplify and measure effectively. There are many pieces that enter into neighborhood management, most of which are abstract and difficult to measure. However, this is also

an area heavy in research that can be of use in examining what encompasses neighborhood management. Neighborhood management refers to a community's ability to come together in order to take a level of control over what happens within the neighborhood. Peterman (2000) highlights two main issues that affect a neighborhood's ability to manage itself. First is the development of linkages among people who live and work within the community. It is difficult for any one person to have a serious impact on a neighborhood. However, as people begin to connect with one another their ability to impact what takes place in their neighborhood increases (Peterman 2000, 34). Therefore, the creation of linkages among residents is one of the key factors to be taken into account when examining community development efforts in regard neighborhood management. However, internal linkages are not the only factor affecting a neighborhood's ability to effectively manage itself. External linkages are also important. Many things that could or do impact neighborhoods originate outside the neighborhood itself. For this reason, linkages with resources outside the community have a powerful impact on a neighborhood's capacity to manage itself.

These concepts come from a somewhat simplified version of a complex body of research concerning the role of social capital in neighborhood development that was spurred by the work of Robert Putnam (1995). However, social capital is not the same as neighborhood management. Some argue that social capital alone does not necessarily lead to effective neighborhood management. Although the specific role played by social capital is debated, there is general agreement on the role of internal and external linkages (referred to in the debate over social capital as bonding and bridging social capital), which is why they will be included here. However, the idea of social capital and the

development of internal and external linkages do not include all that goes into effective neighborhood management. To begin with, social capital theory does not explicitly include the role of institutions and linkages between institutions. Local institutions often play a key role in community development. Effective local institutions and those institutions' ability to work with local residents and one another is another important factor shaping a community's capacity for managing itself. In addition, a neighborhood must also be able to compete effectively with other neighborhoods for resources. If a neighborhood is not effective at obtaining resources it will be unable to become a neighborhood of choice. Both the role of institutions and a neighborhood's ability to compete for resources will be analyzed along with each model's ability to generate internal and external linkages. These four factors will be used to measure how well a particular model assists a neighborhood in managing itself.

Each model and illustrative example will be examined in regard to its ability to affect each of the factors discussed above. As each model and illustrative example is examined, only the areas where the model or illustrative example organization has an effect, either positive or negative, will be discussed. It can be assumed that any factor which is not discussed in regard to a particular model or organization has been excluded because the model or organization in question has no discernable effect in that area.

Although admittedly general, the framework described above is well suited for the development of a typology. The framework is somewhat limited by not directly addressing issues such as safety or crime, and instead attempting to measure more macro level factors such as neighborhood image. However, there are two important reasons for utilizing this framework. One, the size and scope of this study does not permit a more

detailed analysis and doing so is not necessary to establish the basic typology that is the goal of this paper. Secondly, this type of analysis works well with the data collected, both from the literature and from the illustrative examples. Because of the comprehensive nature of the study, variations exist in the literature on the various models. Each model has not been examined in the same way in previous research. Utilizing a somewhat general, macro level evaluation framework allows for the integration of these various bodies of research. Although simplified, this evaluation framework will be more than adequate for framing a discussion of the differences that exist between each of the models.

CHAPTER 3: Methodology

3.1 Identification of the main models

Identifying and analyzing the various models of community development is not a simple or clear cut exercise. Clearly identifying and describing each of the main models of community development, developing a typology for analyzing the different models in relation to one another, and examining their effectiveness at accomplishing a wide range of goals requires a clear methodology that must be adhered to uniformly for each of the models. A systematic series of steps must be taken in order to properly research, organize, and develop a useful typology that can fairly and effectively compare a wide range of models and outcomes.

The process of developing the typology begins with research to identify the main approaches or models of community development. These main approaches are identified by researching the wide range of approaches that exist and then analyzing the unique nature of organizations engaged in community development to understand patterns which linked these organizations together in meaningful ways. Each organization has its own history, structure, goals and programs. In addition, each organization exists in a unique neighborhood with a unique set of actors. However, it is not the purpose of this study to describe the differences between each individual organization, but rather to highlight the common features of a handful of general approaches in order to get a clear picture of differences across the various approaches. The typology focuses on differences between the main models rather than focusing on the differences within individual organizations utilizing the same general approach. The intent is not to discover what makes individual organizations successful, based on the specifics of each organization, but to separate the

features of the each of the main approaches and analyze them more generally to discover the areas in which each model has been shown to be effective in.

3.2 Development of an organizational framework

Once the main models or approaches are identified, a framework is adopted to be used as an overall method of organization for the typology. In order to organize the typology in an efficient and effective way, this paper classifies the models based on their level of community participation and control. The amount of community participation and control within community development organizations has a great impact on the goals and structure of the organization and therefore the organization's overall approach to community improvement. This method of organization has been shown to have a large impact on the origin, structure and effectiveness at impacting the various aspects of community improvement that characterize the range of models (Keith 1996). Although there are other possible methods of organization, this method has been seen as effective in separating models across a continuum (Lane and Dorfman 1997). Organizing the typology in this way allows for a spectrum of models of community development to be identified ranging from approaches which rely completely on community participation and in which control is exercised completely from the bottom-up, to approaches where control is exercised completely from the top-down and no community participation is taken into account. The spectrum exist between these two extremes, with various balances of community participation and decision making power existing in between.

3.3 Examination and evaluation the models

Once the main models have been identified and the method of organization has been selected, the next step is to describe each of the selected models in detail. Each description focuses on the historical background or basis for the model, the typical structure of an organization fitting this model, and the areas of community development in which the model is theoretically most effective. The historical background of each model is important because it provides insight into both the original intent of the model and how that intent and the model may have changed or adapted over time. The structure of the organization is important both for defining each model and for describing how the model operates. The structure is where the key differences between models lie and is what separates the models from one another. Finally, examining the dimensions of community improvement for which each model is theoretically best suited serves as a basis for comparing the organizations. The first two pieces of the description are fairly straightforward, while the last piece requires a bit more clarification.

3.4 Completion of Illustrative Examples

The next step is the completion of illustrative examples of each model, which are used to provide examples of how an organization typical of each model functions in a real world context. As mentioned earlier, although different organizations may follow the same general approach, each organization is unique and functions in a unique setting. Utilizing illustrative examples will provide a concrete example of each model, how it functions, and in what areas it is effective. The illustrative examples will examine organizations in Cincinnati, Ohio using primarily in-person interviews, augmented by

analysis of relevant organizational and outside documents. Interviews are conducted using a framework developed by Twelevetrees (1996). Each illustrative example will mirror the theoretical description of the model it represents by focusing on the organization's history, structure, and outcomes.

The theoretical models and illustrative examples are then used to develop a complete typology of community development models and their areas of effectiveness. The final step is to evaluate each model, its place in the typology and relevance for community development. This analysis includes the conclusions that were reached and suggestions for further research.

3.5 Summary

In order to complete the typology of community development approaches, models must first be selected. Once selected, they are examined and evaluated based on the expanded neighborhoods of choice framework. This step is followed by highlighting illustrative examples of each model from the Greater Cincinnati area. Finally, conclusions are drawn from these findings.

CHAPTER 4: Typology of Community Development Models

Before embarking on the typology itself, it is important to understand some points about its structure. As discussed in Chapter 3, the models were selected after careful research and consideration. The scope of this paper necessitates selecting only five models. A typology of this size cannot include every possible model and as a result the typology is not completely comprehensive. There are approaches that do not fit well within any of the identified models, as well as approaches which combine aspects of more than one of the identified models. In fact, in a real world setting, many organizations exist on the margins between two of the identified models.

However, the purpose of this study is not to describe every possible approach to community development. Rather, this work attempts to identify some of the main approaches, with an emphasis on including models across the spectrum. In other words, this typology attempts to be all-encompassing without not being completely comprehensive. The aim was to select models so that approaches which do not neatly fit within any of the identified models can be shown to combine characteristics of models which have been identified and examined. Doing so allows the typology to accomplish its goals while staying within the parameters afforded in this study.

Figure 1: Typology and Illustrative Example Overview

Source: Author 2006

4.1 Community Organizing

The community organizing model has the highest level of community participation of any model in the typology. Community organizing groups typically result from grassroots actions to involve large numbers of local residents and business leaders and engage them in actions to improve conditions within their community.

4.1.1 History

Community Organizing has a long history dating back to the settlement house movement (Stall and Stoecker 1998) and the civil rights movements (Morris 1984) in the early 20th century, but the development of modern day community organizing began in the 1930s with the controversial and confrontational tactics of Saul Alinsky¹ (Ross and Levine 1996). His tactics drew heavily from the early labor movement but he applied those strategies to organizing within neighborhoods in order to help local residents gain the power to affect conditions in their communities. The first organization to use such a model was Alinsky's Back of the Yards Council, established in 1939 to help residents fight against the despicable conditions in their workplace and community created by the meatpacking industry in Chicago. The Back of the Yards was widely successful in both organizing residents and leveraging the power of people in numbers with that of local institutions such as churches and unions (Horwitt 1989, 225). Alinsky then went on to found many more similarly patterned organizations throughout the country. The Industrial Areas Foundation (IAF), which he founded, continues to train organizers (including this author) and sponsor organizing efforts throughout the country.

¹ Saul Alinsky (1909-1972) was considered the father of community organizing. A critic of modern liberalism, Alinsky's work, including the Founding of the Industrial Areas Foundation (IAF) and the books *Reveille for Radicals* and *Rules for Radicals*, sought to create structures to promote populist democracy.

However, Alinsky was not only successful in directly creating organizing groups, but had an impact on most, if not all, subsequent organizing efforts as well. Most modern organizing efforts are either patterned after Alinsky's ideas or a direct reaction to them. What set Alinsky's organizing apart from previous efforts was his use of aggressive, in-your-face tactics that allowed local residents to confront individuals or institutions that held power over the community (Alinsky 1972). Alinsky's organizing framework is based on the idea that many, and perhaps even most, citizens are powerless to affect what takes place in their community. The purpose of Alinsky-style organizing is not to assume direct control of the neighborhood but instead to force those in power to enact the will of those who alone are powerless. The ideas and methods Alinsky developed form the basis of almost all modern day community organizing efforts.

However, not all organizing efforts are patterned directly from Alinsky's ideas and methods. While some have directly borrowed from Alinsky, others have built on or modified Alinsky's ideas. Since Alinsky introduced his style of organizing, subsequent community organizers have often modified his approach based on one or two main criticisms. First, many organizers reject Alinsky's style, which is seen by many as overly aggressive and obnoxious (Peterman 2000, 44) and instead propose strategies that focus on neighborhood assets as building blocks for effecting change within a neighborhood (Kretzmann and McKnight 1993). They argue that organizing can be both more successful and sustainable when focusing on a community's assets rather than its needs and shortcomings and adjust their model accordingly. Secondly, others feel that Alinsky does not go far enough by simply forcing those in power to react and instead advocate strategies that focus on allowing previously powerless citizens to participate in self-

governance (Kotler 1969). They argue that citizens should not simply try and fight the powers that be but instead should work to assume power for themselves. While these modifications to Alinsky's basic model create some variation in approach between community organizing organizations, they all follow the same basic community organizing model originally developed by Alinsky.

4.1.2 Structure

Community organizing efforts are initiated in a variety of ways and for a variety of reasons. Often a single contentious issue will spur local residents to organize to address the issue. At other times deteriorating conditions within a neighborhood will cause some residents to say "enough is enough" and begin to organize to combat the perceived decline of their neighborhood. Community organizing efforts also can be instigated by a local institution or institutions, often a church or other non-profit organization that sees some need for change within the community. However, once the impetus is there, each effort follows the same general model.

No matter what instigates the process, organizing generally begins with a series of individual meetings, i.e., two or three individuals sitting down to discuss their thoughts and feelings regarding their neighborhood. The idea is to use the meeting as a way to draw out issues or subjects that are important to the individuals. The meetings can be conducted by a professional community organizer (whose role will be discussed in detail later) or by residents themselves. The number of individual meetings varies depending on a number of factors including the size of the neighborhood and the number of actors involved, but enough meetings must be held to include a significant percentage of

neighborhood residents and they often number in the hundreds or even thousands. The primary goal of the individual meetings is to identify a number of issues that are important to the majority of the residents who participated. The secondary goal of these meetings is to begin to develop relationships and a network among the residents of the community that serves as the foundation for the group.

Once the individual meetings have taken place, the most significant themes have been identified, and relationships have begun to be developed, a large community-wide meeting (or a series of smaller group meetings) is held. In this community-wide meeting the residents in attendance discuss the major issues or themes identified in the individual meetings. The goal of the community-wide meeting is to refine further the issues or themes identified in the individual meetings and select a handful of issues which are most important to the community as a whole. These issues will then serve as the basis for the organization's work.

Once these issues or themes around which the organization will work are identified, groups are created to research, develop, and carry out plans or "actions" regarding each issue. These groups are usually referred to as "teams" or "action teams" and generally number between two and ten. Each team is made up of a small number of local residents or property owners who have an interest in the issue that is the focus of the action team. The teams serve as the basic structure for most organizing efforts. Each team meets on a regular basis and it is in these meetings that the research is done and plans for action are developed. The majority of the organization's work takes place within the action teams. However, decision making is usually reserved for larger group

meetings to which all local residents are invited and which typically are held on a semi-annual basis.

Community organizing organizations typically work on issues such as crime/safety, schools/education, housing/physical conditions, environment/beautification, and art/culture. A typical action team will work on a single issue, research that issue with regard to the neighborhood and develop a set of plans to address the issue or build on the neighborhood's existing assets. The team will then select a plan of action and submit it to the larger group for approval. If approved, the organization then will move to implement the selected plan. For example, an action team focused on crime/safety might collect crime statistics, interview residents and police officers, and research methods used by other communities. Armed with this information they will then develop a plan of action, for example, regular meetings with police to identify areas of high crime-related activity and the installation of lights in areas of the neighborhood which are dark at night. The action team then would submit these plans to the local residents at a large group meeting to which the group would choose whether or not to adopt and implement the action team's proposal. This is the typical structure through which an organizing effort works to affect community development issues.

However, community organizing efforts usually need the assistance of a full-time community organizer. The organizer's role can vary by organization but the organizer is generally responsible for coordinating the activity of the organization. Organizers are often utilized heavily in starting up the organization, usually to get the interview process moving forward. Organizers can have varying degrees of power to make decisions on behalf of the organization but generally are only authorized to make day-to-day decisions

while the selection of plans and the overall direction of the organization are left to the residents themselves.

Community organizing organizations are primarily funded through grants from foundations and other non-profit organizations and/or donations from participants or sponsors. In addition, there are several national organizing groups, such as the IAF, which support local chapters throughout the country. However, these groups tend to work city-wide rather than within a particular neighborhood.

4.1.3 Effectiveness

The structure of the community organizing model lends itself to impact neighborhood management and image. However, aspects of the model make it difficult to work within the structure of the model to create physical change in the community that would result in improvements to both the community's physical and market conditions.

4.1.3.1 Physical Conditions

Community organizing can have a limited impact on the physical conditions of a neighborhood. Community organizing is well suited for allowing residents to recognize a specific area within the community in need of physical improvement and for giving them the tools to instigate and/or implement that improvement (Smock 2004, 181). However, although community organizing organizations frequently undertake activities such as audits of neighborhood conditions and use them to improve conditions in specific areas, the horizontal structure of organizing groups makes decision-making cumbersome and often prevents them from having a serious impact on community-wide physical

conditions. Similarly, organizing organizations might develop programs to help homeowners make improvements to their homes, slightly improving the housing stock, but the lack of capital resources often allows for only small scale programs in this area. In addition, community organizing organizations are handicapped by a lack of capital and development expertise that renders the model ineffective in affecting the overall physical conditions of a neighborhood (Stoecker 2001). In summary, organizing groups are only able to have a minimal impact on the physical conditions of a community.

4.1.3.2 Market Conditions

The community organizing approach is not well suited for affecting real estate markets. The lack of ability to spur or create development and the minimal effect the organizing model generally has on the image and physical condition of a community combine to limit the impact the model can have on market conditions. Community organizing can in a small way act as a stabilizing force within the market by giving residents and business owners hope for the future of the community. However, these effects are secondary at best and do not have the impact on markets that is typically associated with physical or economic development. As a result, community organizing has a minimal effect on local market conditions.

4.1.3.3 Image

Community organizing is often less effective at impacting a neighborhood's image, but still can have some positive results in this area. While the literature is filled with references to community organizing's success in the area of neighborhood

management, there are far fewer references to its effect on the neighborhood's image as viewed by both those inside and outside the community. However, there is evidence that, to those outside the community, organizing groups can act as a positive voice speaking out in support of the community. In addition, the mere presence of such an organization can improve the neighborhood's image by signaling that local residents care about conditions in their community. To those inside the community, the organizing model can have a greater effect on how the community is viewed. Those participating in the effort will likely have a greatly improved perception of the community and some of that perception may spill over to other residents. However, only the largest, strongest, and most visible organizing groups have a strong effect on a neighborhood's image.

4.1.3.4 Neighborhood Management

The literature on community organizing clearly suggests that it is most effective in the area of neighborhood management. The development of social capital (Vidal 1998), including both internal and external linkages, and the ability for a community to compete for resources (Peterman 2000) are seen as the key outcomes of community organizing. The literature highlights community organizing's ability to develop both internal and external linkages, which in turn helps individuals improve their own lives and residents come together to improve conditions where they live (Vidal 1998, Peterman 2000). Community organizing improves internal linkages by creating opportunities for residents to interact and work with one another. In addition, the organizing model creates forums that provide opportunities for the creation of external linkages to those in power and other resource providers outside the community. Furthermore, community

organization provides a the means for communities to fight for resources by giving local residents a forum to express their views concerning neighborhood conditions and affairs, and by providing them opportunities to act on those views. Furthermore, the organizing model not only creates a powerful institution within the community but can also act as a mediator or unifying force between other existing institutions. When undertaken successfully, community organizing is able to create internal and external linkages for community members, can act as a unifying force connect institutions within the community, and can empower communities to fight for resources.

4.1.4 Conclusion

The organizing model, with its reliance on interactions between and among individuals and groups, assist greatly in developing a neighborhood's capability to manage itself. The structure of the model, particularly its high level of involvement of community residents and business leaders, permits this approach to have a tremendous impact on neighborhood management. In fact, almost every aspect of the model is geared towards some aspect of neighborhood management. The model's ability to impact neighborhood management also translates into a significant capacity to impact neighborhood image, even if this is often not a direct focus. The positive feelings about the neighborhood that can be generated by this approach and the number of individuals and groups involved result in a strong ability to impact positively both internal and external neighborhood image.

However, the characteristics of the model that make it so effective at neighborhood management hinder its capacity to impact the physical and market

conditions within a community. Lack of capital and expertise, combined with a horizontal structure that does not lend itself to real estate development, hinder community organizing's ability to make major improvements to the physical conditions of a neighborhood. As a result, the model is also limited in its ability to effect market conditions. In conclusion, the structure and origins of the community organizing model make it well suited to impact neighborhood management and image but at the same time limit the ability to work within the model to affect the physical and market conditions of a neighborhood.

4.2 Community Development Corporations

Community Development Corporations (CDCs) are the next step up the ladder of community involvement from community organizing, involving less community participation and control than organizing but more than the other models. CDCs were originally envisioned as locally-controlled organizations that could help to fill in some of the gaps left by grassroots organizing efforts by combining some local control with a focus on physical and economic development. However, over time CDCs have evolved from this initial ideal and have become a unique approach to community development with a structure and a set of outcomes unrelated to their activist origins. CDCs are generally defined as non-profit entities, serving a low-income community, with a community-led board, and engaged in physical or business development (NCCED 1995).

4.2.1 History

Community Development Corporations have undergone a significant evolution over the last five decades. The earliest CDCs developed out of local political groups in the mid-1960s as an attempt to empower local residents. The Bedford-Stuyvesant Restoration Corporation, founded with assistance from Senator Robert F. Kennedy, is widely acknowledged as the first CDC. The Bedford-Stuyvesant Restoration Corporation was focused on improving the physical conditions of the New York neighborhood in which it is located, one that had seen dramatic demographic shifts in the preceding ten years. The organization's goal is to improve local conditions in order to attract outside investment to the community (Peterman 2000). Most other CDCs at the time followed a similar strategy and were generally activist organizations that focused on housing and business development. During the 1960s less than 100 CDCs were formed, mostly by community activists seeking to augment their grassroots organizing efforts.

However, as the number of CDCs grew to several hundred during the 1970s, foundations became interested in them and began to increase the available funding. In addition, the development of the federal Community Development Block Grant (CDBG) provided more opportunities for funding. These opportunities led to a shift away from CDCs roots as activist and organizing related organizations. Government and foundation funding allowed CDCs to grow from their origins as complements to organizing efforts. During this time CDCs not only grew rapidly in number, but also became more specialized and the majority of CDCs began to focus primarily on housing. Many CDCs were actively engaged in fighting redlining and combating the impact of urban renewal.

It is during this time period that CDCs came to be seen as a unique and important element in the overall community development landscape.

Throughout the 1980s and 1990s the number of CDCs continued to grow rapidly. Presently there are well over 2000 CDCs operating in the United States. Over time CDCs continued to become more specialized and the majority of CDC today are focused primarily on housing development. As a result, their staffs became more specialized professionals with experience in many aspects of housing development. Ninety percent of CDCs are engaged in housing production (NCCED 1995) producing roughly 23,000 units each year (Walker 1993). Housing production makes up the bulk of CDCs' work and is their greatest contribution to community development.

4.2.2 Structure

Like community organizing groups, CDCs can be formed in a number of ways. They may be formed with the help of local government, develop out of an existing neighborhood institution, or begin as organizations intended for non-development work (organizing, advocacy, etc.)but which, over time, began to undertake development. Regardless of how a particular CDC is formed, there is a general structure that is typical for most CDCs. CDCs were intended to be organizations controlled by the local community (Green and Haines 2002) and as a result most CDCs are controlled by a board of directors either largely or wholly composed of local residents (Peterman 2000). However, many question the true level of community control for a number of reasons. To begin with, as CDCs have become more specialized and focused on housing production, many have begun to rely more heavily on, and often even defer to, the

expertise of the professional staff (Stocker 1998). Although many rely heavily on voluntary participation (mostly from board members), almost all CDCs employ some professional help ranging from project specific consultants to numerous full-time professional staff.

As project financing has become more complex due to changes in federal policy, professional staff with expertise in the various areas of housing development have become increasingly important (Peterman 2000). This has led many board members to feel they lack the technical expertise to exercise the control they were intended to have, weakening the level of overall community control (Green and Haines 2002). In addition, others have questioned the level of community control that exists by simply using a representative board. In all, there is little evidence or reason to believe that the majority of CDCs are fully community controlled. However, through ties to local government or through locally controlled boards, most CDCs have some element of community participation and control.

In addition to the board of directors, most, but not all, CDCs rely on at least some professional staff. The size of CDCs can vary widely. The smallest and least active CDCs may have no professional staff at all and many rely on volunteers and board members to complete their work, but doing so limits their ability to have a strong impact in the community. However, the typical CDC utilizes at least a handful of staff members. Usually a CDC is headed by an executive director, who oversees all of the corporation's work. CDCs also may utilize a number of other staff members to assist or manage various projects or specific aspects of the work in which they are engaged. This may include a director of housing and/or economic development. Some CDCs have larger

staffs that may be separated into different departments, but such cases are rare. Most CDCs get by with an executive director and a few additional staff members, who handle all of the day-to-day work of the corporation.

As with differences in staff size, CDCs vary with regard to housing production. Over 70% of the over 2000 active CDCs produce fewer than 25 new or rehabbed housing units per year (Southland 1999). This corresponds with the small staff size that is typical of most CDCs. However, a smaller number, less than 6%, produce over 100 new units each year (Southland 1999). These CDCs require a larger staff size and may also support their housing activities by managing their properties and/or engaging in economic development activities. Only a small percentage of CDCs engage in direct economic development activities, usually related to supporting the local business district (Green and Haines 2002). In summary, the typical CDC is comprised of a volunteer board of directors, at least partially drawn from the community, and a handful of professional staff members who engage primarily in housing production, creating less than 25 new units each year.

4.2.3 Effectiveness

Community development Corporations' explicit focus is on improving physical and market conditions, primarily through housing production. However, their structure results in unique outcomes in each of the areas of the neighborhoods of choice framework.

4.2.3.1 Physical Condition

CDCs have a positive effect on the overall physical conditions of a neighborhood. CDCs' focus on housing production allows them to be particularly successful at improving the physical condition of neighborhoods' building stock. CDCs are flexible enough to hire outside professionals with the development expertise that organizing organizations often lack. Their small size and the relative ease of their decision-making process make them ideal for physical development. CDCs can have a fairly strong positive impact on the building stock of a neighborhood through their primary focus, the creation and rehabilitation of housing units. Although most CDCs only engage in a few relatively small projects each year, over time they can have a more lasting impact. In addition, new housing produced by CDCs generally either replaces deteriorating or abandoned properties or occupies previously vacant land, which leads to positive environmental impacts by eliminating blighted areas that often are home to poor environmental conditions.

4.2.3.2 Market Conditions

CDCs can have a strong impact on a neighborhood's market conditions. CDCs can improve or stabilize housing values by stimulating new development and/or decreasing the number of blighted areas in a community. Doing so helps to stabilize or increase property values in the surrounding areas. The small size of most CDCs is not as great a limitation as might be supposed because of the strategic nature of CDC projects. Small, targeted investments can go a long way toward stabilizing the overall market (Gittell and Vidal 1998), while having a smaller impact on a neighborhood's overall

building stock. For this reason, CDCs have the strongest impact on neighborhood market conditions despite their relatively small size.

4.2.3.3 Image

CDCs have a slightly positive impact on neighborhood image. New housing production, particularly rehabilitation and infill development, can have a positive impact on a neighborhood's appearance. This can have a positive effect on how people feel about the community. However, the impact may be limited by the size of the projects undertaken. Most CDCs' small size allows them to undertake only a limited number of projects which may not be enough to counteract other negative forces acting in a community, such as its perception as a high crime area. In addition, small projects may receive little attention outside of the community and therefore fail to change the image of the community held by those outside the neighborhood.

4.2.3.4 Neighborhood Management

Community Development Corporations generally are not successful at affecting neighborhood management. CDCs have been widely criticized for not addressing the needs of the citizens, particularly those living in poverty, who live in the communities in which they operate. CDCs have been widely criticized because they "often lack staff with management skills and are frequently unprepared and ill-equipped to deal with the social and economic problems of their low-income tenants and the neighborhood problems that affect the ability of the CDC to keep good tenants in their building" (Peterman 2000, 51).

In other words, CDCs themselves do not act as a strong institutions within their communities and do not link well with other institutions within the community.

In perhaps the most stinging critique of CDCs, Stoeker (1997) states that CDCs' structure, especially their focus on physical development and reliance on educated professionals from outside the community, results in their inability to affect social and economic issues facing neighborhoods. Stoeker goes on to argue that rather than attempting to solve neighborhood problems by creating internal and external linkages with and among local residents, CDCs act to soften residents' willingness to come together to impact the social order. Although some dispute Stoeker's arguments, there is general agreement that at best CDCs fail to help neighborhood management and some would even argue that they can act as an obstacle to the development of a neighborhood's management capabilities.

4.2.4 Conclusion

CDCs are generally small organizations staffed by a handful of professionals who focus primarily on the production of housing. They are typically overseen by a board of directors partially derived from the communities in which they serve. The thousands of small CDCs throughout the country have a narrow focus that results in limited outcomes. CDCs are good at affecting the real estate markets and improving the physical conditions of a community by engaging in targeted development, primarily new housing.

Although originally envisioned as community-controlled organizations, CDCs' focus on physical development and market improvements requires small professional

staffs with expertise in real estate development to handle the majority of work, which often translates into a decrease in community participation and control. This lack of community input leads to nonexistent or even negative impacts on neighborhood management. CDCs' effectiveness makes them powerful tools in neighborhoods which already have strong neighborhood management characteristics but lack ideal physical and market conditions. However, the model is limited by its size and focus in ways that impact its ability to make significant improvements to neighborhood image and management.

4.3 Comprehensive Community Initiatives

Comprehensive Community Initiatives (CCIs) are organizations which attempt to improve neighborhoods by taking a multifaceted approach which typically includes economic and physical development, human and social services, and neighborhood management activities (Brown 1996). Although these organizations vary somewhat in terms of structure and approach towards community development, they share many aspects that make them a unique model of community development. CCIs can rely on significant participation but more often rely on information from and about the community without allowing community control over any of the organization's activities.

4.3.1 History

Like many of the other models, Comprehensive Community Initiatives are deeply rooted in the history of community development that serves as the foundation for the

majority of the models discussed in this study. In addition, like many of the other models, CCIs have evolved over the last 15 years to become a unique approach to community development.

Throughout the history of community development, many researchers and practitioners have understood the need for comprehensive approaches. The settlement houses of the 19th century are some of the first manifestations of this idea (Halpern 1995). Settlement houses offered neighborhood residents a wide variety of services that attempted to meet most of their possible needs. This concept was revived in the 1960s, first with the Ford Foundation's Gray Area project and subsequently with a number of other programs, including many initiated by the federal government. At the same time CDCs began to be formed with ambitions to become comprehensive approaches to community development in their own right. However, as discussed previously, the overwhelming majority of CDCs quickly became focused on physical development (although a small number do remain comprehensive, personifying the fluid nature of the typology).

CCI themselves began to grow significantly in numbers in the mid 1990s. Their emergence can be traced to the perceived failure of two other approaches towards community improvement. First, many engaged in "bricks and mortar" approaches to community development rarely are capable of achieving long-term social and economic improvements. Second, most human service efforts have very limited success and have little impact beyond individual cases due to their inability to overcome the overwhelming conditions facing many residents of low-income communities (Kubisch et al. 1997). Most CCIs were formed as a response to these limitations. Many CCIs are organizations

which originally undertook one or the other of these two approaches and have slowly come to the realization that a more comprehensive approach is necessary to achieve the desired results.

4.3.2 Structure

Although the ideas behind this approach are similar in organizations across this model, CCIs manifest themselves in a variety of ways. Chaskin, Joesph, and Chipenda-Dansokho (1997) identify four main methods of operationalizing comprehensive community development strategies. One method involves integrating existing social services. Organizations that undertake this method attempt primarily to integrate existing programs and services, both public and private, to provide a comprehensive clearinghouse for social services in a community. This approach attempts to overcome some of the limitations of the social service system, including fragmentation and duplication (Bruner 1991). CCIs that utilize this method typically are limited to providing services and are the least likely to be formed from an existing organization. Organizations that make use of this method will not be the focus of the discussion of CCIs in this work, as they are the least comprehensive due to their lack of focus on physical development.

Another of the main methods identified by Chaskin, Joesph, & Chipenda-Dansokho (1997) involves the parallel provision of activities. This strategy involves advancing a wide range of social services programs in tandem with physical and economic development efforts without expressly linking the two. This enables organizations employing this method to provide a comprehensive agenda but does not

fully integrate the approaches. This can become problematic when attempting to develop a distressed community in a holistic manner, as the progress that is made can be piecemeal.

A third method involves integrating development strategies across physical, economic and social development (Chaskin et al. 1997). CCIs that use this method take the next step from parallel provision and look for ways to link programs from various areas. Integration allows these organizations not only to provide a comprehensive range of programs but also provides opportunities for programs to build upon one another and address the complex nature of problems affecting communities.

The final method identified by the authors involves organizations that begin by focusing on efforts in one area and expand incrementally into other areas. The most common manifestation of this method involves a social service agency or community organizing effort recognizing the need for social, physical, and economic development and, over time, developing programs in this area. However, organizations can develop in the opposite manner. Incremental development toward comprehensiveness is the most common of the four approaches, as it builds on existing organizations, which reach various levels of comprehensiveness.

These four methods are not mutually exclusive. For example, an organization may build incrementally towards the parallel provision of services or towards integrating activities across social, economic, and physical boundaries. For the purposes of this study, the following discussion and related illustrative example will focus on organizations which have built incrementally towards comprehensiveness because they are the most prevalent and at the same time attempt to integrate activities across physical,

economic and social boundaries, and are the most effective at achieving positive community change (Chaskin et al. 1997). However, it should be kept in mind that there are many organizations which may use differing combinations of these approaches and offer various levels of comprehensiveness.

Comprehensive community initiatives typically are non-profit organizations, governed by a board of directors. The board may or may not be made up of community representatives, but typically has at least some community representation. A CCI model can be undertaken city-wide, but most are specific to a single neighborhood. Although they vary in size, most have much larger staffs than any of the other models discussed in this typology. This is because a large staff is required to undertake and integrate the variety of activities undertaken by CCIs. CCIs tend to be structured more like a traditional small- to medium-sized business, with various departments responsible for different activities.

4.3.3 Effectiveness

The goal of comprehensive community initiatives is to affect communities across the various dimensions. Theoretically they should be equally successful in all areas identified as relevant within the neighborhoods of choice-based evaluation framework. However, the size and complexity of the organizations required to undertake such comprehensive community development is difficult to achieve, resulting in most CCIs failing to have a strong impact every area. In other words, their comprehensive nature allows that to have some effects in all areas, but CCIs are in most cases unable to have

equal success across all areas and typically are most successful in the area that was at the heart of each individual organization's original mission.

4.3.3.1 Physical Conditions

Typically, CCIs are typically moderately successful at affecting the physical conditions of a community. As mentioned earlier, more often than not CCIs emerged from social service or community organizing backgrounds and over time added physical and economic development activities to bolster the overall effectiveness. In such cases, the expertise and resources devoted to physical development often are less than those devoted to activities related to neighborhood management (Chaskin, et al.1997). There are cases in which CDCs or other organizations focused on physical development have incrementally added neighborhood management activities. These organizations have stronger impacts on physical development but such organizations are seen less frequently than those having emerged from social service backgrounds.

4.3.3.2 Market Conditions

As with to their effect on physical conditions, CCIs' impact on market conditions depends on their area of focus. Typically, CCIs have a slight positive effect, but in cases where this is the organization's principal focus the effect can be much stronger. For example, some organizations focus on physical development and linked homeownership support programs, in which case they can have a strong impact on residential market conditions. Likewise, if an organization's focus is on business development or support programs, it is likely to have a powerful impact on commercial market conditions. Some

organizations may even be able to have strong impacts in both areas. However, doing so comes at the expense of strong impacts in other areas (Gittell and Vidal 1998).

4.3.3.3 Image

CCIs can have important impacts on neighborhood image due to their large size and comprehensive programs. These factors make these organizations more visible, both inside the neighborhood and through local media attention. The organizations' numerous programs reach a significant percentage of local residents which results in a high level of visibility within the community. In addition, CCIs are large enough to gain local media attention. In both cases the reaction to the organization is mostly positive, resulting in a positive impact on the neighborhood's image. In addition, because they engage in diverse programming, CCIs may engage in activities directly aimed at improving community image. In total, CCIs are fairly effective at impacting internal image and may have an impact on external image as well.

4.3.3.4 Neighborhood Management

CCIs can have strong impacts on neighborhood management, particularly the role of institutions in the neighborhood. The majority of CCIs began as organizations focused on these areas and as a result devote the most resources and have the most expertise in activities related to this area. Most involve some community organizing, bringing the benefits discussed earlier, albeit slightly diluted by the lack of community involvement and the impact of other activities. In addition, many CCIs have strong social service components which provide an opportunity to expand these serves to include programs to

improve neighborhood management. However, as discussed with physical and market conditions, their impact depends on their area of focus, which is not always in this area. Overall, CCIs have the ability to have a strong impact on neighborhood management.

4.3.4 Conclusion

Comprehensive community initiatives are the most successful of all the models at affecting each of the four areas identified by the neighborhoods of choice framework. The fact that CCIs utilize community input without giving up control allows them to have a noticeable impact on physical conditions, market conditions, image and neighborhood management, all at the same time. This ability is augmented by the large staff size and businesslike structure. However, in the majority of cases, CCIs are much stronger in one or two areas related to their historic origins or the explicit focus of the organizations. Organizations can have difficulty fully integrating all of their diverse programs and as a result focus on what they do best or what they perceive as a core need. This area is often at the same time bolstered by the variety of programs related to it and watered-down by the drain of resources to other areas. The end result is effectiveness being spread across more factors at the expense of the kind of strong impact other models may have in a particular area. However, although in practice most organizations do not reach the model's goal of complete comprehensiveness, the CCI approach provides a bridge between the more extreme models. By integrating community input but retaining full control, CCIs are able to have a more balanced impact on all the areas in the neighborhoods of choice framework.

4.4 Local Government

Local governments can be structured in many different ways, but many share a similar approach to neighborhood community development. This approach attempts to utilize extensive federal funding in a way that balances neighborhood and city-wide concerns. The result is often a strong focus on the physical conditions of neighborhoods, with little attention given to specific neighborhood concerns relating to management, markets or image.

However, local government is a unique model because it often acts as a resource to other models and undertakes community development in its own right. One of local government's main functions is attempting to increase the capacity of other community development efforts. Yet, local government plays a role in direct development as well. For this reason it has been included as a model within the typology, as opposed to a tool for assisting other models. Nevertheless, it is important to recognize the dual role that local government plays in impacting community development.

4.4.1 History

Throughout its history the U.S. Federal government has attempted to intervene in local community development to varying degrees. Although community development is thought of as a local government undertaking, most local action has been dictated by federal policy. This is because the federal government provides the bulk of the funding that is the backbone of local government community development efforts. However, despite the ability to enact overarching community development policy through legislation and large-scale funding, federal policy has been an inconsistent mixture of programs that often shifts dramatically with changing presidential administrations

(Keating and Smith 1996). For these reasons, a brief history of federal policy and its relation to local governments is helpful in understanding the general evolution of government intervention in community development.

Although limited government intervention in community development took place before the World War II, the post-war era was the beginning of significant government involvement in community development. Urban Renewal was the first major government program to address the issues facing deteriorating urban communities. Beginning in 1949, Urban Renewal was intended to redevelop blighted areas by bulldozing and rebuilding large tracts of land within low-income communities. Although the program had some success stories, it has been largely criticized for destroying the fabric of communities and displacing hundreds of thousands of people. In addition to policies such as urban renewal that were directly aimed at community development, the government enacted several policies in the post-WW II era that had drastic, although unintended, consequences for local communities. The expansion of the interstate highway system and housing policies that aided new home construction began a dramatic shift to the suburbs that had profound negative effects on urban communities. Overall, federal policy during this era, although often well intended, had destructive effect on urban communities.

In the 1960's federal policy shifted away from urban renewal towards a more grassroots approach. The War on Poverty was initiated as an attempt to empower the poor and give them more control over the communities in which they lived (Keating and Smith 1996). However, the program was largely unsuccessful due to lack of funding and resistance by local political figures. However, several important programs were founded

during this period, including head start, legal aid, and the model cities program. In 1965, the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD) was formed to both coordinate federal community development efforts and give them a higher profile in national policy debates. Although the majority of federal programs enacted during this period were relatively unsuccessful, many had a lasting impact on how local governments approach community development.

The 1970's are perhaps the most important period in the history of federal community development policy. Another shift took place during this period that continues to shape federal policy toward local government community development. In 1973, federal funding for community development was converted from many specific grant programs to a single comprehensive grant, the Community Development Block Grant (CDBG). CDBG are awarded through HUD based on a formula designed to determine local need. These funds are regulated to ensure that they are used to benefit low- and moderate-income communities but are intended to give local governments more control over how and where money is spent. Although the formula used to determine funding and other minor aspects of the program have changed over the years, CDBG remains the most important source of funding for local government community development. Another important development during this time was the creation of the Section 8 housing voucher program, which was designed to disperse low income residents throughout cities by offering them vouchers to seek housing in the private market. Like CDBG, the Section 8 program remains in place today, although it has not been as successful in deconcentrating poverty in urban communities as it was intended to be (Turner, Popkin, & Cunningham 2000).

In the late 1970s, two laws were passed to help fight discrimination and increase investment in low-income communities. The Home Mortgage Disclosure Act (MHDA) was passed to help prevent lending institutions from redlining and otherwise discriminating on the basis of race. The passage of this law helped local communities fight redlining, a process by which lending institutions refused to give loans based on the racial makeup or income level of a particular community, regardless of the financial health of the individual or individuals requesting a loan. The legislation helped to increase investment in many poor communities throughout the country that had previously been unable to obtain financing. The Community Reinvestment Act further aided investment in distressed communities. The Community Reinvestment Act requires banks to invest in each of the communities they serve. Both these programs significantly increased the ability of communities to attract private investment. In all, the programs of the 1970s, many of which are still in place today, have shaped the future of federal community development policy and in the process have had a profound affect on how local governments administer community development.

Throughout the 1980s and early 1990s HUD's funding was dramatically decreased, resulting in long waiting lists for federal housing subsidies and deteriorating conditions in many urban communities. Mismanagement and bureaucratic holdups by HUD officials further exacerbated the problem. Several new programs were introduced, including the empowerment zone concept, but have had little impact (Keating and Smith 1996). There has been a shift towards a stronger focus on economic development, which has been reflected in changing guidelines for the use of CDGB funds to allow for flexibility to utilize funds for diverse economic development uses. Although some of the

specifics of the program have changed, CDBG remains the starting point for most local government community development efforts.

4.4.2 Structure

The discussion of the changes in federal community development policy sets the stage for the discussion of the structure of local government community development today. Throughout the country, local governments are structured somewhat differently. The relative power of the city council, mayor and in some cases the city manager, all have important effects on how a city functions. Similarly, the structure and organization of city departments has a large impact on where the government focuses its attention and how resources are utilized. For this reason it is important to analyze the structure of each specific local government to fully understand both the priority given to community development and how its functions are administered.

However, there are some general principles most local governments follow when engaging in community development efforts. Although almost all of the work of local governments has at least some impact on neighborhoods, in most cities the functions directly tied to community development take place within one or more specific departments of the local government. Cities may have specific departments dedicated to planning, neighborhoods, and/or community development, all of which may engage directly in activities that fall under the banner of community development. Local governments' commitments to different aspect of community development can vary greatly. The size and relative strength of the departments within the local government can provide a clue as to a particular government's priorities in regard to community

development. For example, a large planning department that reports directly to the mayor can signify a strong commitment to planning within a local government.

Analyzing how a local governments community development functions are structured can go a long way towards understanding a cities priorities and in turn the areas where local government is effective.

Although local governments function somewhat differently, many local governments share a similar approach to community development. It is common for local governments to engage in community development at a neighborhood level, comparable to what Checkoway (1984) describes as “subarea planning”. (Although planning and community development are not interchangeable, the models described in the fairly extensive literature on planning can be used to as a starting point to describe related community development efforts that have been subject to less theoretical and empirical study). In this model, community development and planning activities are initiated, directed, and coordinated at the city-wide level. However, many of the specific functions of community development are deconcentrated and handled at a neighborhood level. Generally, the programs undertaken in the name of local government community development rely on citizen participation, rather than citizen control. In other words, citizen input is collected, often the bare minimum required to receive federal funding (Checkoway 1984), but control remains in the hands of municipal officials. Local government often engages in behaviors that can be seen as informing, consulting, and placating local citizen, all of which are characteristic of the middle of the spectrum of participation and control (Arnstein 1969).

In the subarea planning model of community development employed by most local governments, decisions are made on a neighborhood level, but are influenced by federal, state, and city-wide objectives more than neighborhood specific concerns. Federal programs often dictate strict requirements that local governments must satisfy in order to receive funding. Even CDBG, which was originally designed to give local government more control, has requirements set by the federal government that must be met for funds to be allocated. Not only that, the requirements have changed over time in response to shifts in thinking about community development at the federal level. State governments function in a similar manner, providing funds for specific programs that often leave local governments with limited discretion as to how money is spent. The burden of federal and state requirements for funding, combined with the broad priorities of local government, leave little room for decision making at the local level. Add in the lack of citizen control and the end result is a heavily bureaucratic, top-down system of administering community development programs.

Although the subarea planning approach is typical of local government community development efforts, some governments engage in a more grassroots approaches. Checkoway (1984) calls these approaches “neighborhood planning”. However, he does not clearly spell out how these approaches function beyond the describing them as more bottom-up than subarea planning efforts. Peterman (2000) builds on Checkoway’s concept by tying them to two famous planning approaches: Davidoff’s advocacy planning and equity planning, which is championed by Krumhloz. Advocacy planning (Davidoff 1965) involves planners’ abandoning the idea of remaining value-neutral and becoming advocates for the neighborhoods or groups they represent.

Equity planning is an attempt to empower underprivileged citizens by undertaking programs and policies to increase the range of choices available to them (Krumholtz 1982). Although neither approach results in direct community control, they increase the power of local input to affect both the process of planning and community development. However, these tactics have only been utilized in a few cities and often have been associated with specific progressive city administrations and as a result ended when the administration was removed from office (Peterman 2000).

Most local government planning and community development remains primarily top-down.

4.4.3 Effectiveness

Local governments' primary tool is funding and for political reasons government officials find it easier to spend that money on projects which produce tangible results in a relatively short period of time. The results are a unique set of outcomes for this community development model, primarily focused on physical development.

4.4.3.1 Physical Conditions

Local government can have a strong impact on the physical conditions of a community. The majority of federal funding is earmarked for efforts to provide local communities help with “bricks and mortar” solutions to community issues, including the majority of CDBG funding (Peterman 2000). Through such programs municipalities can have a strong impact on the building stock of the community. In addition, local governments, again with federal funding, are responsible for the establishment and

upkeep of local infrastructure. Similarly, local governments can apply for federal money to do environmental work. Local governments have a greater impact on a neighborhood's physical conditions, primarily through improvements to infrastructure and building stock, than any of the other factors.

4.4.3.2 Market Conditions

Although it is often done indirectly, local government can have a significant impact on local market conditions. Improvements to infrastructure and building stock can help stabilize declining markets. In addition, tax incentives such as property tax abatements and tax increment financing can be utilized to make both homeownership and commercial real estate investment more attractive. Perhaps most importantly, local government investment in a community can be seen as a stabilizing force which can act to calm fears surrounding a neighborhoods' future and in the process help to steady declining markets. Taken alone or acting together, each of these tools of local governments can have positive effects on real estate market conditions within a community, but the effects are indirect and therefore usually cannot single-handedly turn around declining markets.

4.4.3.3 Image

Local government has little to no effect on the image of specific neighborhoods. In fact, in an attempt to gain resources, political and municipal officials are more likely to highlight the negative aspects of a community than to speak about it positively. This is true because a significant concentration of efforts in a particular community by the local

government often signals that the neighborhood is in desperate need. In addition, any media coverage associated with government project is likely to focus on the project rather than the neighborhood itself. In all, there is little the local government does to promote positive images of individual neighborhoods.

4.4.3.4 Neighborhood Management

Local government has little effect on a neighborhood's ability to manage itself. Local government may provide funding or assistance to local individuals or institutions, but does not help to foster internal or external linkages. Likewise, government does little to connect residents to or support local institutions. Local governments lack the participation by local residents that is necessary to effectively impact the community's ability to manage itself. However, local government can help to facilitate neighborhoods in fighting for resources. Local government is often the arena in which neighborhoods must battle with other neighborhoods for funding.

4.4.4. Conclusion

Local government community development is effective at improving the bricks and mortar of communities through programs to provide funding for development and infrastructure improvements and in the process, with the aid of tools such as tax benefits, can positively impact real estate markets. However, as a result of the model's lack of community participation and the limits placed on government, local government community development does little for the image of local neighborhoods and even less for neighborhoods' ability to manage themselves. However, the government does

provide a platform for neighborhoods to fight for resources. Local governments' primary power is control of funding, which translates into a strong ability to improve the physical conditions of neighborhoods. This can have a significant effect on neighborhoods in need of investment in building stock and infrastructure. However, the local government cannot by itself rescue distressed communities due to the limitations the model has on impacting markets, image, and neighborhood management.

4.5 Business Leadership Coalitions

Although there are other top-down, privately controlled efforts that impact communities, the focus of this section of the typology will be on what are known as business leadership coalitions (BLCs). BLCs were selected as the focus of the far end of the typology because their efforts are explicitly aimed at community development and because of the comparatively large impact they have relative to other private, top-down efforts. There are several other forms of private sector involvement in community development besides BLCs, all of which involve little or no community participation and control, but the other private efforts are generally not explicitly aimed at community improvement and/or usually do not take place on a neighborhood scale. For example, many private real estate development companies may be involved in projects in low-income neighborhoods that can have very real, positive effects on the community. However, these efforts are usually undertaken to make a profit rather than to benefit the community and therefore do not have explicit community improvement goals. In addition, these efforts typically are one project and not a coordinated effort to improve

conditions in a community. It also should be noted that many of the CDCs and CCIs discussed in earlier in the typology are also technically private organizations. However, CCIs and CDCs have specific ties to a neighborhood and its residents unlike most BLCs which undertake their efforts with little or no community involvement. In addition, BLCs have specific characteristics, such as funding sources, that make the model and its outcomes unique. For these reasons the discussion of the low community involvement, top-down end of the community involvement spectrum will center on BLCs.

4.5.1 History

BLCs have been around for many years but have begun to undertake community development efforts for approximately the last 20 years. When they first originated, BLCs were primarily business-only entities made up largely of CEOs and gave business leaders a forum to come together and share their concerns about their community (Austin and McCaffrey 2002). However, the last 20 years have brought a proliferation in public private partnerships (PPPs) that has given BLCs opportunities to move from a discussion of community affairs to direct involvement in community development action. However, not all PPPs involve BLCs and not all BLCs are limited to involvement in PPP. For these reasons it is important to understand the relationship between PPPs and BLCs.

To begin with, it is important to define Public Private Partnerships. PPPs are partnerships between two or more actors who enter into a long-term relationship in which each partner must both bargain for itself and have a stake in outcomes. PPPs have a much longer history than Business Leadership Coalitions. PPPs were first seen in the mid-nineteenth century (Beauregard 1998) and their role increased in the post-World War

II era with the development of federal programs such as Urban Renewal (Stephenson 1991). They first became an explicit part of federal community development policy in 1978 and many local governments have felt they are increasingly necessary to offset decreases in federal funding for community development that began in the 1980's and continue today.

BLCs began to play a role in PPPs in the 1980's and their involvement has grown significantly in recent years. Before heavy BLC involvement, PPPs usually were partnerships between local governments and local non-profit community development organizations (such as CDCs or CCIs) which provided those organizations with government funding for specific projects in return for some government oversight of those projects. In contrast, when BLCs began to enter into partnerships with local government, the result was a true sharing of power and resources. BLCs typically engage in PPPs that undertake large-scale projects focused on urban development, neighborhood rehab, and/or major projects such as development of sports stadiums (Austin and McCaffrey 2002).

PPPs involving BLCs were largely successful at achieving their aims, which consisted mainly of economic development projects focused on new real estate development in central business districts and nearby dilapidated neighborhoods (Krumhloz 1999). However, these partnerships and their resulting projects received criticism for neglecting the low-income residents of these neighborhoods (Krumhloz 1999; Harvey 1993). However, these criticisms did not slow BLC participation in community development. Rather, many BLCs became more independent in pursuing their community revitalization goals, relying less on local governments in order to avoid

red tape and shield political figures from such criticism. In such arrangements, local governments often continued to contribute funding for BLC-led projects but lost much of the oversight they had previously enjoyed.

Although BLCs and PPPs can be clearly differentiated, their histories are intertwined. PPPs have given BLCs a foothold in community development in many cities throughout the country. Recently many BLCs have taken that initial foothold and expanded into more autonomous community development efforts.

4.5.2 Structure

BLCs are slightly different in regard to their make up, the projects they engage in, and the nature of their relationships with the local government and other institutions. However, most fall within a narrow range of possibilities with regard to each of these facets of their makeup. To start with, BLCs, as mentioned previously, have historically been composed of the CEOs from large, local corporations. In recent years many BLCs have begun to include the leaders of large institutions such as universities and other prominent local leaders outside of the business sector. However, the idea that BLCs are “made up” of local business leaders is somewhat deceiving. Business and civic leaders make up the board of directors of BLCs that are engaged in community development. These leaders serve as the driving force behind the organizations. The board is responsible for setting the direction of the organization and all decision making but in order to engage directly in community development, BLCs must employ a professional staff. The staffs of such organizations are typically very small and highly skilled in real

estate, finance, and development. They carry out the work of the organization as directed by the board.

BLCs also vary slightly in regard to the projects in which they engage. Some are formed explicitly to tackle one problem, such as the development of a large sports complex, while others undertake rehabilitating an entire community. Although their members are likely drawn from throughout the metropolitan area, almost all BLCs focus their attention on the city's downtown or a specific neighborhood therein. For this reason most BLCs fit well into this typology, which is focused on neighborhood level community development efforts.

BLCs also differ in their relationships with other organizations, particularly the local government. As discussed previously, many BLCs enter into what are called PPP with local governments. However, the current usage of the term PPP has come to stray from its original definition, as laid out previously in this paper (Rubin & Stankiewicz 2001). Many so-called public-private partnerships are not the balanced, power-sharing entities they are purported to be. Many BLCs dominate local governments in PPP, and only rely on governments as one of several sources of funding. Local governments often provide CDBG money, provide tax breaks, contribute infrastructure, supply bonds, and/or give tax increment financing to BLCs. BLCs then construct complicated financing schemes to get projects done. As a result, it is difficult for all but the most sophisticated professionals to understand or participate in the process, leaving most local citizens out of the game (Krumholz 1999). Furthermore, the complicated nature of the deals often make it difficult to determine who is ultimately responsible, allowing the business leaders driving the projects and the local government leaders facilitating their completion to take

credit for their successes and duck criticism for their failures. Thus, BLCs are able to pursue their agenda with little pressure to account for the needs and desires of the community.

4.5.3 Effectiveness

Business Leadership Coalitions bring a unique set of tools to community development and consequently have a distinctive impact on the communities they target for improvements. However, the top-down, elite driven nature of the model brings with it some limitations. As a result, BLCs are very effective in some areas and ineffective or even detrimental to neighborhoods in other ways.

4.5.3.1 Physical Conditions

BLCs have the tools to be extremely effective at improving the physical conditions of a neighborhood. BLCs' ability to mobilize money, the expertise of the business leaders and organizations' staffs, and the clout that the business and civic leaders can bring to a project all combine to make BLCs extremely effective at improving the physical conditions of communities (Austin and McCaffrey 2002). These tools enable BLCs to engage in major projects to develop or upgrade infrastructure, rehabilitate large amounts of building stock and to instigate environmental cleanup. Most BLCs' main focus is on bricks and mortar projects to improve neighborhood conditions (Austin and McCaffrey 2002). BLC's focus on and uniquely suited skills in this area allow BLCs to affect the physical conditions of neighborhoods in a dramatic fashion. In many ways BLCs are like super CDCs. They engage in similar work but have significantly more

resources and expertise and are not limited by community control in any way. This allows BLCs to act very similarly to CDCs in regard to the physical conditions within a community but on a much larger scale.

4.5.3.2 Market Conditions

The size and scale of the physical improvements BLCs are capable of translate into serious impacts on local real estate markets. In fact, although improving physical conditions for the public good may be the stated goal of many BLCs, in reality many business leaders volunteer time to such efforts in order to protect the current investments and assets of their corporations by stabilizing or improving markets in the areas where they are located (Harvey 1993). Such efforts have been criticized for doing so at the expense of low-income residents (Harvey 1993; Krumholz 1999). However, for the purposes of this examination, it is clear that as a community development model, BLCs can have a dramatic impact on local real estate markets in the communities they target, more so than any of the other models.

4.5.3.3 Image

The size of BLCs projects can have a strong positive impact on the external image of a community while leaving many local residents feeling left out and subsequently lowering their impressions of the community. BLCs can have such a strong impact on physical and market conditions that they can “turn around” a neighborhood in the eyes of outside observers. However, this often comes at the expense of local residents, lowering their impression of the community and their place in it. Because local residents have

almost no say in or control of the processes reshaping their community, many may feel helpless, even if the changes are otherwise positive. This can and often does breed resentment in the community and results in a lowering of internal public opinion about the neighborhood.

4.5.3.4 Neighborhood Management

BLCs often do not have a positive impact on neighborhood management. BLCs bring significant resources to a community but do not increase the neighborhood's capacity to compete for its own resources. Furthermore, as mentioned previously, BLCs' community revitalization efforts often have been criticized for displacing or isolating local residents. In such cases BLCs can have a negative impact, not only by failing to provide opportunities to create new linkages among residents, but even by breaking down some existing linkages. In addition, BLCs often are at odds with local institutions and their efforts at community improvement (Krumholz 1999). A frequent result is often infighting among institutions within the community that leads to bad feelings at best and inaction at worst. Taken as a whole, BLCs do not engage in any activities to involve or engage local residents that might help to improve neighborhood management and some of the activities BLCs engage in may even be a detriment to it.

4.5.4 Conclusion

BLCs have the ability to have tremendous impacts on physical and market conditions. Like CDCs, BLCs can translate their small size and significant expertise towards real estate development and market improvements. However, unlike CDCs,

BLCs typically have significant capital resources and superior professional expertise at their disposal. The end result is a stronger impact on physical and market conditions than CDCs, but at the expense of even worse performance in regard to neighborhood management and internal image. BLCs' effect on internal neighborhood image and management highlights the problem many have with this model, namely that it is helpful to those outside the community at the expense of many of those within it. However, the major impact BLCs can have in a community cannot be ignored. The structure of these organizations, their leadership and their financial backing, combined with their avoidance of public input and control, allow them to obtain results at a level not approached by any of the other models. However, these successes are limited to physical and market conditions and often come at the expense of neighborhood management and internal community image.

CHAPTER 5: Illustrative Examples

The following illustrative examples are based on interviews conducted by the author, documents created by the organizations, and local media coverage. Each illustrative example utilized at least two interviews. Where possible these interviews included both an individual within the organization and an individual who is not part of the organization but is intimately familiar with its work. The illustrative examples' structure mirrors that of the typology so that comparisons can easily be made between the two. These examples are based primarily on organizational self reports and as a result could overstate organizational accomplishments in some cases. These illustrative examples are not intended to be in-depth case studies. Rather, they are intended to give a general picture of actual organizational structure and outcomes in order to provide more concrete examples of each of the models presented in the typology.

5.1 Community Organizing - Price Hill Will

Price Hill Will is a grassroots organization dedicated to improving the neighborhood and in turn the lives of local residents. Price Hill Will is perhaps the best example of a community organizing effort currently active in Cincinnati. Although the organization is still in its infancy, its beginnings and its basic structure offer a good real world example of the average community organizing model.

5.1.1 History and Structure

5.1.1.1 Neighborhood Background

Before discussing the organization's structure, it is necessary to set the context in which the organization was formed. The neighborhood's background and history are particularly important for understanding the context in which the model is placed. The neighborhood of Price Hill has seen several important shifts over the last 200 years. Located in the western hills of Cincinnati, Price Hill offers breathtaking views of the Cincinnati skyline and from the late 1880s through the turn of the century, Price Hill was able to capitalize on those views by attracting upper class residents to move up the hill to escape the expanding manufacturing district below in the Mill Creek Valley. However, throughout the 20th century, the neighborhood slowly transformed into a solid blue-collar neighborhood that typifies the city's west side. During the second half of the 20th century the neighborhood saw few changes as the community functioned as a solid middle class enclave. However, recent years have brought changes to the community that have unsettled this historically stable neighborhood.

The redevelopment of Cincinnati's two largest housing projects², both located on the western edge of the central business district, directly down the hill from Price Hill, brought an increase in low income residents using Section 8 housing vouchers (Osborne 2003). At the same time many middle class families who had lived in the neighborhood for generations fled to more suburban communities to escape what they perceived as trouble associated with the neighborhood's newest residents. These two factors are the primary reasons why in recent years population has declined, vacant housing has increased, and housing values have declined to the point that they are some of the lowest

in the city (Arnold 2005). In addition, although overall neighborhood crime statistics have remained relatively stable, several high profile incidents have transformed the neighborhood's image in such a way that many believe it to be unsafe. This perception was further reinforced with a front page feature article focusing on East Price Hill, hyping the neighborhood's decline and nicknaming it "crack hill" (Arnold 2005). While it is unclear whether the cause of the neighborhood's problems are due to the influx of low-income households or the resulting exodus of middle class families, the end result has been the steady decline of the neighborhood (Troendle 2004).

5.1.1.2 Organizational History

Residents witnessed the beginning of the neighborhood's decline into instability long before it came to the attention of local media. Beginning in 2002, local leaders sensed the neighborhood was in trouble. In response, Imago³, a local non-profit focused on environmental issues and based in the neighborhood, applied to the a coalition of funders that included the United Way, Fifth Third Bank, Proctor and Gamble, and the Greater Cincinnati Foundation for a small grant, worth \$100,000 over three years, as part of the coalition's Community Improvement Project (CIP). Imago was one of three organizations selected for funding, making Price Hill one of the program's three focus areas.

Originally, Imago planned to use the money to focus on a small area encompassing roughly three square blocks that only accounted for a fraction of the neighborhood. However, Imago's staff quickly realized that in order to make a significant impact on the neighborhood, they had to expand the scope of the project to

include the entire neighborhood (Musser 2006). Imago then formed a steering committee of involved local residents and the leaders of several community institutions, including local non-profits, schools, churches and businesses to form a strategy for using the money that would have an impact on a neighborhood scale.

At this point, the steering committee was still strongly connected to Imago and relied on the organization for direction, funding, and other resources. However, the steering committee quickly began the search for an effective organizing strategy.

After researching several organizing models, the committee settled on Appreciative Inquiry, a method developed by Chet Bowling of Ohio State University. Appreciative Inquiry is a method of organizing that focuses on interviewing local residents and attempting to get them to focus on things they appreciate within both the community and among their neighbors (Bowling 2002). Appreciative Inquiry is a slightly more personal take on the widely popular asset-based community development model.

5.1.1.3 Structure

With the Appreciative Inquiry method as a basis, the steering committee began to build an organization using the community organizing model. Using Appreciative Inquiry as a framework, the steering committee, with Bowling's assistance, developed a set of interview questions to use as a basis for talking to local residents (Bowling 2002). Over the next several months the organization collected input from over 2,000 individuals, primarily through interviews and surveys. Volunteers comprised of local residents and students conducted the interviews and surveys and then processed the information they had collected in order to highlight the main themes drawn from the

interviews (Musser 2006). Once all the information had been processed by volunteers, a large meeting was held at which all Price Hill residents were invited to discuss the themes identified during the interviews. With these themes as a guide, the residents formed eight groups, each focused on one of the identified areas. These groups became the Community Action Teams (CATs) that form the backbone of the organization (Price Hill Will 2005).

Over time the CATs have remained the backbone of the organization (Musser 2006). The CATs are focused on arts, beautification, business, block clubs, churches, diversity, environment, housing, safety, schools, and youth. The CATs meet monthly to discuss issues and formulate action plans related to their chosen issue. The housing CAT has been the most active, developing a “buy, improve, sell” program to turn around the neighborhood’s depreciating housing stock. A local resident leads each CAT and runs the monthly meetings. Originally, AmeriCorps volunteers also provided assistance with the day-to-day operations of the organization. However, as the organization has grown, it required the addition of two full-time staff members, one to focus on the organizing effort and one solely focused on housing. In addition, the steering committee now serves as the organization’s board of directors, which, with staff assistance, is responsible for day-to-day decision making. The CATs, made up of neighborhood residents, remain the driving force of the organization and are responsible for its overall direction. Overall, Price Hill Will fits closely to the traditional organizing model.

5.1.2 Outcomes

Although Price Hill Will is relatively young, some areas of success and some aspects in which the organization is lacking can be identified. The organization's effectiveness at using the community organizing model to impact the four areas identified by the neighborhoods of choice framework was evaluated based on interviews of local staff and residents and local media coverage.

5.1.2.1 Physical Condition

Price Hill Will recognizes the need to make improvements to the physical condition on the neighborhood, but has had little impact in this area. To begin with, the "buy, improve, sell" program has only finished one house as a test run of the program (Musser 2006), which to date has had almost no impact on the deteriorating housing stock. The organization's own estimate is that roughly 20% of the housing stock (roughly 250 single family houses) would need to be revitalized in order to have a significant effect on the market (Musser 2006). Similarly, the organization has undertaken some neighborhood assessments to catalogue the condition of the area but nothing yet has come from these assessments (Witte 2006).

The organization's structure makes it difficult to easily affect building stock, environmental conditions, or infrastructure of the neighborhood. Although the organization is attempting to impact the building stock, housing redevelopment requires expertise in a number of areas, from finance through construction and sale, in addition to significant capital. However, both capital and expertise are somewhat lacking within the neighborhood (Witte 2006). The City of Cincinnati has been a significant help on the

capital side but local residents are still developing skills and expertise in the necessary areas, a process that is aided by Price Hill Will's housing director. However, to date the structure of the organization and its reliance on local residents' time and skills has made it difficult for the organization to have a strong impact on the physical conditions of the neighborhood.

5.1.2.2 Market Conditions

The organization realizes that turning around the real estate market is necessary in order to halt the neighborhood's decline and as a result has made increasing housing values and boosting the local business district key goals. However, the organization still has a long way to go. The City of Cincinnati has pledged \$630,000 to assist with the "buy, improve, sell" program and the planned marketing efforts are intended to give the real estate market a boost. However, to date the only house that has been redeveloped under the program has yet to be sold. The organization has also begun efforts to improve conditions in the local business corridor in order to attract investment in vacant commercial spaces but has yet to have any concrete success in this area. Although the organization involves a large percentage of the neighborhood's residents, these residents and the organization itself have limited financial resources that hinder its ability to have an affect on the real estate market. On the whole, the organization is still far from making any substantial progress toward impacting the real estate market.

5.1.2.3 Image

The neighborhood's decline, real or perceived, has had a large impact on Price Hill's image. However, the organization has been able to impact neighborhood image in several ways. For example, the newspaper article that painted a profoundly negative portrayal of the neighborhood (Arnold, 2005) was followed by a coordinated effort to get a series of letters to the editor printed in the local newspaper (Musser 2006). The letters were written by residents associated with the organization and each defended the neighborhood and the progress being made. In addition, the organization itself has been portrayed as a force for positive change in the community by the local community (Pierce 2006). Currently, the organization is focusing on a slogan and other marketing materials that highlight the positive aspects of the community (Musser 2006). Price Hill Will is able to involve a large number of community members, in the process improving the perception of the community among those residents. That involvement has helped create a positive image of the organization in the media (Pierce 2006). Local residents hope that positive image can be expanded to include the neighborhood itself. On the whole, the organization is beginning to have a strong impact on the negative image of the neighborhood that developed in the early 2000s but still has a way to go before completely turning around Price Hill's image.

5.1.2.4 Neighborhood Management

Price Hill Will has had a significant impact on neighborhood management. The thousands of interviews that helped to form the organization brought many residents together. The community action teams give groups of residents the opportunity to have

an impact on a topic related to the neighborhood that is important to them. In addition, Price Hill Will has been able to act as a cohesive force to bring together various community organizations and institutions that had previously not worked with one another (Witte 2006). The neighborhood was arbitrarily split into East and West Price Hill in the mid-1990s by the city, which was attempting to develop a series of neighborhoods modeled after the garden city movement that was popular at the time (Musser 2006) and over time each neighborhood developed its own community council, schools, and other civic institutions. These organizations and institutions developed sometimes conflicting agendas and often fought with one another. Price Hill Will has been able to act as a bridge between these organizations to enable them to work together toward common goals (Witte 2006). By bringing together residents, organizations, and institutions throughout the neighborhood, Price Hill Will has been able to give the neighborhood power to manage its own affairs. As a result, the organization has been successful in attracting grant money from both the City and local foundations. In all, Price Hill Will has had a profound impact on neighborhood management.

5.1.3 Conclusion

Price Hill Will formed according to the prototypical organizing model of interviews and community meetings. The organization is managed by a small staff that relies on community residents for the bulk of the organization's undertakings. The organization is governed by local residents' input and the direction of community leaders. This reliance on community residents has had a strong positive effect in the area of neighborhood management and a smaller but still important effect on the neighborhood's

image. However, the lack of skills and resources within the neighborhood has hindered the organization's ability to impact the neighborhood's physical condition and real estate market.

Price Hill Will's outcomes match the potential effectiveness of the community organizing model as described in the typology. The strengths of the model, its ability to impact neighborhood management and image, are mirrored in the successes of Price Hill Will. Likewise, the model's shortcomings in regard to physical and market conditions are reflected in Price Hill Will's difficulties in impacting the neighborhood's physical and market conditions. Overall, Price Hill Will fits within the parameters described in the discussion of community organizing within the typology.

5.2 Community Development Corporations – Lincoln Heights Community Improvement Corporation

The Lincoln Heights Community Improvement Corporation (LHCIC) is a non-profit community development corporation formed in 2002 by the Village of Lincoln Heights. (A community improvement corporation (CIC) is a community development corporation that has a board of directors composed of at least one-third government officials.) LHCIC supports local commercial and residential real estate development within the neighborhood to help solidify the Village's tax base. LHCIC is representative of a typical CDC model in size, structure, and the types of activities it undertakes.

5.2.1 History and Structure

5.2.1.1 Neighborhood Background

The Village of Lincoln Heights is a first-ring suburb located approximately 12 miles north of Cincinnati in the Interstate 75 corridor. The village is predominantly African-American and has approximately 4,500 residents. It is one of the poorest communities in the Cincinnati area, with a high unemployment rate and a low median income (Monk 2005). At the time LHCIC was formed, the Village's image was suffering due to serious financial troubles and media portrayals of the neighborhood as a "war zone" of out of control crime (Kempe 2004). In addition, the village's building stock, 70% of which was over 30 years old, was significantly deteriorated and over 10% of the community's homes and buildings were vacant by 2002 (Howard 2003). In 2002 the Village had over 1,700 housing units, many of which were in need of renovation or repair. These facts paint the picture of a community in serious need of revitalization.

5.2.1.2 Organizational History

The Lincoln Heights Community Improvement Corporation was formed in October 2001 by the Village of Lincoln Heights. The organization spent its first two years identifying its objectives and completing a residential and commercial market study rather than directly engaging in any community development efforts (Kanters 2006). However, in April 2003 the organization applied for funding through the Local Initiatives Support Corporation (LISC) and was able to secure funding to hire an executive director and secure office space. With the executive director on board the organization was able to move beyond the planning phase and begin its work in earnest.

At this time the organization began work on the objectives its board of directors had established during its first two years. The organization's focus is primarily to improve residential and commercial real estate markets by improving physical conditions and in the process attracting new residents and businesses to solidify the village's tax base (Kanters 2006). With these goals in mind, the organization has undertaken residential and commercial space rehabilitation, new home construction, and brownfield redevelopment. LHCIC currently holds over \$1.4 million in real estate assets and has revenue streams totaling over \$300,000 annually (Kanters 2006).

5.2.1.3 Structure

The organization is governed by a twelve member board of directors composed of one-third local government officials and two-thirds community residents and local business owners. The local government officials include the mayor, councilmembers, and the chief of police. The board directs four professional staff members, including the executive director, two project managers and an administrative assistant. The staff have considerable decision making authority within the overall objectives of the organization (Kanters 2006). The executive director is responsible for overseeing all the corporation's activities, including oversight of all projects, community relations, and coordination with the board of directors. Together, the board and the executive director make up the leadership of the organization.

The remaining staff focuses more on specific projects. The project managers are responsible for oversight of specific projects and initiatives. Currently LHCIC is engaged in several large projects including the relocation to the village of the City of

Cincinnati's Police firing range, the construction of seven new homes as part of the Jackson Homes project, and a major brownfield redevelopment project on an old industrial site within the village. The two largest current projects are the Jackson Homes and the potential relocation of a Cincinnati Job Corps Center to the brownfield site. The Jackson Homes project includes seven new single-family homes that will complete the long stalled Martin Luther King Estates. The Jackson Homes project began in late 2005 and is relying on a \$274,000 state grant and \$210,000 in federal HOME funds acquired through Hamilton County's community development department to keep the seven homes affordable to low-income families. The use of outside funding sources, primarily grants, in this project is typical of every LHCIC project to date.

The relocation of the Cincinnati Job Corps Center is an ongoing project involving significant environmental cleanup. Currently, LHCIC is awaiting approval for a grant to clean the 24 acre site. The project would include a \$30 job training center focused on delivering job training to teens and young adults. If the project were to go forward it would require significant work on the part of LHCIC to secure the necessary funding and approvals. The Jackson Homes project and the relocation of the Cincinnati Jobs Corps Center are the largest current initiatives and are good examples of the type of work in which LHCIC engages.

In addition, LHCIC recently bought and rehabilitated a collection of rental properties, the income from which will serve as the basis of the organization's operation budget going forward (Kanters 2006). This will allow LHCIC a measure of independence but the organization will continue to rely heavily on funding from LISC and government programs to complete the majority of its projects. Each of the projects

the organization undertakes requires large subsidies from one or more of these sources and the revenue stream for the new rental units will not be large enough to replace these sources. The organization continues to work to identify opportunities for development within the objectives laid out by the board of directors and to compose creative plans to make that development a reality.

5.2.2 Outcomes

LHCIC is for the most part typical of the average CDC; it is fairly effective at impacting the physical condition of the neighborhood and particularly effective at stimulating local real estate markets, but has less of an effect on neighborhood image and neighborhood management. However, the organization is working to improve in the areas in which it is lacking.

5.2.2.1 Physical Conditions

LHCIC has had an impact on the physical condition of Lincoln Heights, through both housing rehab and redevelopment and brownfield cleanup. LHCIC's initial focus has been improvements to the deteriorating building stock. LHCIC has developed 15 single family homes, including 8 on scattered vacant lots and 7 on one large vacant plot as part of the Jackson Homes project (Kanters 2006a). In addition, LHCIC has rehabilitated 17 previously uninhabitable apartment buildings for a total of 32 new rental and homeownership units. These projects were the first new construction or major rehabilitation in the neighborhood in over 25 years (Kremme 2004). Although this is only a small portion of the total units of the community, it is a significant

accomplishment considering the striking lack of new development in the community over the last several decades.

LHCIC has been equally successful in improving the environmental conditions of the community. The organization is unique in this respect. Because of the industrial past of this first suburb, much of the land open for development has some environmental issues. The organization has been successful in securing grants to reclaim these brownfields to make them available for commercial development, a significant contribution to the environmental health of the community. LHCIC also has plans to participate in the development of a community recreation center which would be a strong contribution to the neighborhood's infrastructure.

The organization's success in these areas can be attributed to the expertise of its staff. The development experience of the staff has enabled the organization to engage successfully in housing production and rehabilitation while their professional skills have allowed them to successfully apply for grant money to complete all of the organization's projects (Holmes 2006). It is the professional and development expertise of the staff that allows the organization to be successful at meeting the objectives set by the board of directors.

5.2.2.2 Market Conditions

LHCIC has been most successful at impacting the local market conditions. LHCIC has both brought a significant amount of land for commercial space onto the market and worked to recruit businesses to occupy that space (Kanters 2006). The organization has even been successful in relocating one company to the area. Similarly,

the organization is responsible for the first new residential development in over 25 years and has worked to recruit families from outside the neighborhood to occupy those houses. All of these actions, which have a strong stabilizing effect on a declining market, are made possible because of the expertise the staff members bring from outside the community and the focus in these areas provided by the board of directors (Holmes 2006). These two factors have allowed a very small organization to have a disproportionate effect on commercial and residential real estate in Lincoln Heights.

5.2.2.3 Image

The organization has been moderately effective at impacting the neighborhood's image by working to get positive news published in the local media. However, the articles can only do so much and the LHCIC has done little to improve the internal image of the community. LHCIC has had two positive stories written about it in the local newspaper and two in the local business journal. However, these articles have only gone a little way towards reversing the extremely negative image the village has had since before LHCIC was formed (Kanters 2006). In addition, because LHCIC does not involve many local residents in its projects, village residents are unaware of the projects LHCIC undertakes. If local residents are unaware of the work the organization has done, it cannot have a positive impact on their feelings for their community. The end result is that LHCIC has not had a significant impact on local neighborhood image.

5.2.2.4 Neighborhood Management

The organization does not have a significant impact on neighborhood management. The organization involves in its projects few if any community members outside of the board of director. The organization's board to defines objectives and the staff to executes these objectives, all without community input. There is little opportunity for community interaction or even awareness of the organization that could lead to successful neighborhood management. The organization has been successful in assisting the community in obtaining outside resources in the form of grants, but has not increased the capacity of the community to do so on its own. In summary, the organization's work has no significant contribution to neighborhood management in Lincoln Heights.

5.2.3 Conclusion

Lincoln Heights Community Improvement Corporation is a typical community development corporation. It is effective at utilizing its professional staff to make targeted improvements to Lincoln Heights physical conditions, particularly the building stock and environmental conditions. These strategic improvements translate into a magnified positive impact on an otherwise declining real estate market. However, because the organization involves only a handful of community members, these efforts have a minimal impact on the neighborhood's ability to manage itself. In addition, these projects are on a small enough scale that they have received minimal media attention and even less notice from local residents. In all, LHCIC fits within the abilities and limitations of the community development corporation model. The organization's size

and expertise allow it to be successful using a bricks and mortar approach to stimulate real estate markets but the nature and scale of these efforts does little to impact the neighborhood's management capabilities or image.

5.3 Comprehensive Community Initiatives – The Brighton Center

The Brighton Center is a non-profit neighborhood institution offering comprehensive community development and family support programs. The Center's mission is to enable families and individuals in the community to become self-sufficient. The organization engages in many efforts that fall into the category of social services, outside the realm of community development. However, in recent years the organization has shifted significant resources to pursue community development objectives in order to better complete its core mission. The Brighton Center is a prime example of the comprehensive community initiative approach to community development.

5.3.1 History and Structure

5.3.1.1 Neighborhood Background

Newport is a historic neighborhood located in northern Kentucky, directly across the river from downtown Cincinnati. It was founded in 1795 and remained a small town for many years. However, in the early 1900's Newport gained a reputation as an "anything goes" town that was home to gambling, prostitution, and other illegal activities. Newport retained a somewhat glamorous reputation before the popularity of Las Vegas grew and stole much of the glamour. In the period between 1940 and 1980,

Newport was seen as a corrupt and largely lawless town. Reform began in the 1980s with the banishment of nude dancing and the establishment of a historic district containing over 1,000 homes on the city's east side. In the late 1990's large blocks of commercial development took place along the southern edge of the Ohio River. However, even into the early part of this decade the majority of the city, particularly the west side, remained poor and in need of significant work to become a neighborhood of choice.

5.3.1.2 Organizational History

The Brighton Center was founded in 1966 in a small storefront on the corner of 8th and Brighton Streets. The Brighton Center came about as a result of the work of the Reverend Bill Neuroth, assistant pastor at Corpus Christi Church in Newport, who saw a need to assist the many poor people, mostly from Appalachia, who migrated to Newport as more wealthy residents fled to the suburbs. Many of these new residents were unprepared for living in an urban setting and at the time there were no agencies or community centers to meet the needs of these people. Many did not have jobs and were struggling to get by with no real outside help. The Brighton Center was founded to fill this void by acting as a safety net for needy individuals and families.

The center began as a small office and meeting place with no employees and only a handful of programs aimed at emergency assistance. However, over the years the center has expanded to include 8 departments offering over 100 programs with the help of over 140 full-time employees and thousands of volunteers. In addition, the Brighton Center has expanded its mission from serving families by providing emergency social

services to providing comprehensive community development aimed at helping families and communities reach self sufficiency. The organization is funded through private grants, particularly from the United Way of Greater Cincinnati.

Currently the Brighton Center, Inc. includes administrative offices in the West End Building at 8th & Central, family services and community development departments at the Family Center at 8th & Ann, the Center for Employment Training at 6th & Washington, the child development department and various youth services programs at its 7th & Park location, three large senior housing complexes located throughout Northern Kentucky, a youth homeless shelter that includes a teenage independent living program, and two one-stop job centers. The Brighton Center also has a wholly owned subsidiary, Brighton Properties, which was formed in 1997 and concentrates on developing and managing affordable housing for area residents.

5.3.1.3 Structure

The Brighton Center has come a long way from its grassroots beginnings to become a large and complex organization. The diverse objectives of its many programs and the large staff require that the Brighton Center be run more like a business than a typical non-profit organization. This businesslike organizational structure begins with strong central leadership. Although the organization has a board of directors (consisting almost entirely of individuals who do not live or work in the community), major decision making is in the hands of a handful of top administrators (Pugh 2006). The executive director, chief operating officer, and assistant operating officer are responsible for all major decisions. Below these three individuals are the eight department directors, who

are given some discretion over their individual departments but whose decisions must be guided by the core mission and values dictated by the three key administrators. Whether it is through direct decision making or by dictating a decision making framework, the Brighton Center is controlled through a highly centralized organizational structure that is dominated by a few central figures.

Strong centralized leadership is not the Brighton Center's only businesslike characteristic. The organization also places a premium on accountability. All programs are subject to intense scrutiny and are held accountable for reaching predetermined outcomes. This results in a businesslike organizational culture in which employees feel pressured to reach a broad spectrum of performance outcomes pertinent to the programs in which they work (Woods 2006). In addition, the Brighton Center places a very strong emphasis on leadership development. The Center is focused on developing homegrown leadership that will be able to step into the key leadership roles in the future (Pugh 2006). This breeds a somewhat competitive atmosphere among the staff that is atypical of most non-profit organizations. Overall the Brighton Center has a very business-oriented organizational structure and culture.

However, the organization stays grounded in the community through regular comprehensive community assessments. These assessments utilize interviews with local residents and program participants, as well as focused demographic information in order to get a feeling for both what is happening in the community and what the community's assets and needs are (Pugh 2006). The community assessments are undertaken every three to five years and are used to inform decision making regarding the direction of the organization. The use of community assessments, along with the organization's mission

and values, are the key differences between the Brighton Center and other private non-profit organization not explicitly tied to the community. These factors tie the Brighton Center closer to the community and allow community members to have some impact on the organization.

5.3.2 Outcomes

The biggest difference between the Brighton Center and the other illustrative example organizations is the comprehensive nature of its programs. With varying degrees of success, the Brighton Center attempts to influence each of the four main factors identified by the neighborhoods of choice framework. However, they have more success in some areas than others and the organization's efforts can be stretched thin by attempting to influence such a broad range of issues within the community.

5.3.2.1 Physical Conditions

The Brighton Center has been moderately successful at impacting the physical conditions of Newport. The organization has had a moderate effect on the building stock of the community, a slight impact on the environmental conditions but almost no effect on local infrastructure. The Center's recent effort to build and rehabilitate housing for low-income residents has made measurable improvements to the neighborhood's building stock. The organization has developed over 200 new housing units in older areas of the neighborhood that otherwise have seen no new housing development in the last 25 years (Pugh 2006). The Brighton Center also organizes regular neighborhood cleanup and other activities to help make small improvements to the environmental condition of the

community (Frye 2006). The organization's large staff and significant resources have allowed the Brighton Center to move successfully into housing production (Pugh 2006) and to connect to a large section of the community to organize community cleanups (Frye 2006). Together these efforts make modest improvements to the physical conditions of the community.

5.2.3.2 Market Conditions

The Brighton Center has a small impact on real estate market conditions. The organization has provided a boost to the local business corridor and the related commercial real estate market (Pugh 2006). It has done so through programs to promote local businesses and by working with the city and local residents to remove problem businesses. Together, these actions have helped to spur new development and lower vacancy rates in an aging commercial corridor (Pugh 2006). Similarly, the organization helps to bolster the supply of homeowners in local residential real estate markets by working with homeowners to manage new home purchases, dramatically increasing homeownership and lowering foreclosures in the community. The large staff and businesslike organization of the Brighton Center have made it possible to enter into these areas, which are outside of the organization's historical core activities. Because of its organizational structure, the Brighton Center is able to engage in these diverse efforts that have combined to have an effect, albeit a small one, on the local real estate markets.

5.3.2.3 Image

The Brighton Center has a strong impact on Newport's internal image, but does not have a discernable effect on its image as viewed from outside the community. Events such as the "Brighton the Way" parade, programs to promote the local business district, and the variety of social service programs that serve as a safety net for local residents all contribute to the creation of a positive internal neighborhood image among local residents (Pugh 2006). However, these efforts are largely unnoticed outside the community (Woods 2006). These tendencies are consistent with the organization's mission to assist local residents, rather than improving the neighborhood as a whole. As a local institution, the organization is focused on helping improve the lives of current residents rather than attracting new ones. In doing so, the organization undertakes efforts to improve local residents' image of their community but does not address the external image the community projects.

5.3.2.4 Neighborhood Management

The work of the Brighton Center sets the stage for the development of internal and external linkages, helps to bring resources to the community and is highly successful at connecting institutions with the community. These endeavors permit the organization to achieve a moderate level of success at stimulating positive neighborhood management. However, the organization's focus is diluted by the large variety of programs it offers and it is therefore unable to achieve the highest level of results that otherwise would be possible (Woods 2006). To begin with, the Brighton Center creates opportunities for residents to interact with one another and to connect with important individuals and

groups outside the community but does not take the next step to explicitly create linkages out of those interactions (Frye 2006). Some linkages, both internal and external, are no doubt created, but because this is not the focus of the organization, care is not taken to ensure that the opportunity for permanent linkages created by interaction solidifies into a useful linkage.

Likewise, the organization brings resources to the community but does not increase the neighborhood's capacity to fight for its own resources. The Brighton Center works to bring both foundation grant money and state funding to the community (Pugh 2006), but does so on its own behalf and for its own programs. The organization does nothing to increase local residents' ability to compete for resources on their own behalf.

On the other hand, as a large, far-reaching local institution, the Brighton Center is very successful in involving both itself and other local institutions in the community. The Brighton Center not only is heavily involved in the community, but helps involve other organizations, such as the Newport Business Association and the Newport City Schools, more heavily in the community as well. Overall, the Brighton Center does an adequate job of assisting neighborhood management, but only excels in connecting local institutions to the community.

5.3.3 Conclusion

All in all, as a large, well run organization, the Brighton Center is able to have a moderate impact on almost all the areas identified by the neighborhoods of choice framework. However, due to the large nature of the organization and its far-reaching mission, it is unable to focus in a particular area and have a heavy impact in that area as a

result. These results are consistent with the literature on CCIs. The Brighton Center's original focus on social services remains its strong point, although its efforts to add community development activities incrementally have been moderately successful. In summary, the Brighton Center is able to be more holistic than most organizations engaging in community development, but that comprehensiveness comes at the expense of not having a powerful impact in any specific area identified by the neighborhoods of choice evaluation framework.

5.4 Local Government – City of Cincinnati

The City of Cincinnati has two bodies that explicitly engage in activities tied directly to community development. The Department of Community Development and Planning (DCDP) handles small-scale, neighborhood specific programs and issues while the Economic Development Division (EDD) focuses on large-scale projects. With input from the Mayor and City Council, these two bodies shape city government's role in neighborhood community development.

5.4.1 History and Structure

5.4.1.1 Neighborhood Background

City government is unique in that it does not focus specifically on one neighborhood. However, the City of Cincinnati does attempt to address individual neighborhoods' needs in addition to implementing city-wide programs. Yet because the government's efforts stretch through many neighborhoods, describing the neighborhood

background is needlessly cumbersome. As a result, no specific neighborhood background information is provided.

5.4.1.2 Organizational History

The Department of Community Development and Planning is a relatively new sector of the local government in Cincinnati. The department, as it stands today, was formed in 2003 when the Planning Department was merged into what was the Community Development Department (City of Cincinnati 2005). This followed two previous mergers, both taking place after 1995, that combined what was originally the Office for Neighborhood Housing with the Department of Human Services. The result was a very large City department that is responsible for planning, historic conservation, housing, business development, grant management, and contract compliance. The DCDP offers a wide range of specific programs in each of these areas, the majority of which are focused on a neighborhood level. One of the most important functions of the DCDP is to administer the City's Community Development Block Grant (CDGB) funds. In doing so the DCDP attempts to weigh each neighborhood's needs and equitably distribute the resources at its disposal.

The City's other community development body, the Economic Development Division focuses on larger projects and directs its efforts towards affecting the city as a whole. The EDD was created in 2003 in response to one of the chief recommendations put forth by a special economic development task force formed by Mayor Charlie Luken and Fifth Third Bank president and CEO George Schaefer Jr. The task force was set up as a result of the Mayor's and business community's concerns about the economic future

of the City. There was particular concern among these individuals and groups about the City's handling of many large-scale economic development initiatives. The Economic Development Division was one of the major steps the city took to address this perceived problem.

The Economic Development Division's main objective is to handle the type of large-scale economic development initiatives that many believed were being handled poorly or not at all before the Division's creation. Previously, such projects were handled within the Department of Community Development and Planning. However, the task force felt that department was already so strapped with individual neighborhood-level issues that it was unable to properly address large-scale projects and that, therefore, such projects either failed completely or were unable to get off the ground. The official mission of City of Cincinnati's Economic Development Division is to act as a liaison between the City and developers and to provide financial, technical and informational assistance to promote development within the City (Munitz 2006).

Both the DCDP and the EDD play a key role in the government's community development efforts, but in recent years the EDD's efforts have been the City's main priorities. There are signs that this could change with recent changes on the City Council and in the Mayor's office but for now the City has put its stock in large scale projects run through the EDD and has withdrawn funding from the DCDP.

5.4.1.3 Structure

The DCDP is one of the largest departments of the City government. Although its funding has been slightly reduced in recent years, the Department continues to be a key

part of the City’s budget and is a key mechanism for the allocation of federal community development funds. The Department is headed by a Director who reports to the City Manager’s office and is broken down into four main divisions, each focused on a specific aspect of community development. The Director heads the two largest divisions, business development and housing. A Deputy Director sits below the Director and administers the Planning and Operations Divisions. The Planning Division, which handles primarily land use issues and permitting, was greatly reduced in 2003 when it was added to the DCDP and essentially is a reactive body focusing on administering zoning ordinances. The Planning Division also is responsible for the City’s historic preservation efforts. The Operations Division houses the department’s administration and helps facilitate the allocation of grant money and tax credits.

Figure 2: Department of Community Development and Planning Organizational Chart

Source: City of Cincinnati 2005

The Director oversees the Business Development and Housing Services Divisions. The Business Development Division focuses on assisting small businesses, primarily in the City's Neighborhood Business Districts, and focuses on economically disadvantaged individuals. The Housing Services Division makes up over a third of the DCDP's budget, receiving roughly 70% of the Department's funds. The Housing Services Division focuses on improving housing quality for the City's residents (City of Cincinnati 2005). To this end, the Housing Services Division administers over 20 programs ranging from programs offering assistance and training for neighborhoods, to direct loans for housing rehabilitation, to lead abatement programs, and more (City of Cincinnati 2005). Although programs in the Department's other divisions are important, the work of the Housing Services Division is the DCDP's main contribution to community development.

In addition, the Department was slightly realigned in 2005 with the addition of Development Opportunity Teams (DOTs). There are six DOTs assigned to specific geographic areas (see Figure 3). Each DOT is composed of one employee from the Planning Division, one from the Business Development Division, and one from the Housing Services Division. The DOTs are designed to work with individual neighborhoods to develop three-year plans for neighborhood development and to work to implement those plans. The DOTs have increased significantly the City's focus on individual neighborhood needs when attempting community development efforts.

Figure 3: DCDP Development Opportunity Teams

Source: City of Cincinnati 2005

In contrast to the DCDP, the EDD has a unique place inside City government. The task force and the mayor wanted to ensure that the newly created EDD had the power to get things done, a power that was lacking previously. For this reason the EDD was created, not as a department within the city's regular structure, but as a special division above the department level. The EDD is located within the City Manager's office. The City's structure is such that the City Manager sits atop the organizational chart. All department heads report to the City Manager and the City Manager in turn reports directly to the Mayor and City Council. Below the City Manager are two Assistant City Managers. The Economic Development Director sits at the same level as the Assistant City Managers, a level above the department heads. This structure was put into place intentionally in order to give the Economic Development Director more power than the department heads so that the director could push economic development projects through the city government effectively (Munitz 2006).

The acting Economic Development Director was hired by the City shortly after the division was first created. The division is completely under the director's control. The Director has the power to hire and fire the department's four employees, which include three staff members who act as "front-end" negotiators on economic development projects and one "back-end" compliance officer. The three staff members working on the "front-end" of the economic development process generally are involved in negotiating the terms of deals between organizations and businesses and the City and creating opportunities for further development. The remaining employee works at "back-end," ensuring that the agreed-to terms are upheld by the outside parties with which the city has entered into contracts. These functions are separated in order to enable those employees working on the "front-end" to maintain positive relationships with the people with whom they are working.

The EDD has a line-item budget for day-to-day operations, covering employee salaries, office supplies, etc. However, there is no set limit on the amount of money that is included, either as development cost, tax incentives, or other means, in deals that the EDD reaches with outside partners. The EDD negotiates these agreements with input from the Mayor and City Manager. In most cases, Council must vote on any plan before it becomes final. However, actual spending is left to the discretion of these individuals and Council, which means that Council can appropriate funds or give tax incentives that are not included in the regularly approved city budget. This gives the EDD the power to negotiate large development deals.

Taken together, the DCDP and the EDD are the engine of the City of Cincinnati's efforts to enhance neighborhood community development. Although they pursue their

responsibilities separately, their combined efforts result in the City's contribution to community development.

5.4.2 Outcomes

The City's contribution to neighborhood community development is mostly in the form of funding. The City has access, largely through federal grants and programs, to funding amounts that dwarf most community development efforts. However, this funding is utilized for specific purposes that do not often bring about comprehensive community improvement.

5.4.2.1 Physical Conditions

The City of Cincinnati has a huge impact on the building stock, environment, and infrastructure of the City's neighborhoods, mostly through the administration of federal government Community Development Block Grant (CDBG) money. The DCDP receives roughly \$14 million annually in CDBG funding. Almost all CDBG money is utilized in projects to improve the housing stock and infrastructure of Cincinnati's neediest neighborhoods (Munitz 2006). The City invests heavily in housing production and redevelopment. In 2005 the City contributed funding and expertise to the rehabilitation of over 75 homeownership units and over 250 rental units (City of Cincinnati 2006). In addition, the City provided funding for necessary maintenance on over 2,000 housing units and provided or assisted in funding the creation of an additional 350 new housing units. Together, these upgrades to housing have an impact on the building stock of the communities in which they take place.

CDBG projects are not the only way City government affects the physical conditions of Cincinnati's neighborhoods. The City also has a strong impact on the environmental conditions of the neighborhoods it targets for community development action. The EDD works to spur brownfield development which is made financially viable through government funding and can greatly improve the environmental conditions of a neighborhood. Recently, the EDD arranged to move two companies to a newly redeveloped brownfield in the Bond Hill neighborhood. The City bought the brownfield property and was responsible for its cleanup. In addition to improving the conditions of the environment and building stock, the City is responsible for the maintenance of infrastructure and dedicates a portion of its capital budget to the continual maintenance and replacement of aging infrastructure. Overall the City has a huge impact on the physical conditions of targeted neighborhoods. This is made possible largely as a result of the large amounts of funding made available to the local government for community development purposes.

5.4.2.2 Market Conditions

The City's actions to promote business and improve the local housing stock result in moderate impacts on the real estate market conditions of local neighborhoods. Improvements to the housing stock of a community help to stabilize the market values of surrounding properties. However, because almost all of the City's investment in housing is at the low end of the market, the improvements do not have the type of impact that can strongly push the market. Similarly, incentives for local business development create a small increase in the demand side of the commercial real estate market. However, the

most important impact the City has had is in saving the market from serious trouble by offering incentives to retain local businesses. Without these incentives the local commercial real estate market would see serious decline (Munitz 2006). Again, it is largely federal funding that makes such impacts possible. In all, the City's community development efforts are able to leverage the skills of the staff and federal funding to have a stabilizing impact on local market conditions.

5.4.2.3 Image

The City's community development efforts have no significant impact on the image of its neighborhoods. Cincinnati's neighborhoods have developed distinctive identities over their histories and they are not easily impacted by local government efforts, which are often not focused. Heavy City investment in a neighborhood does not have a strong impact because investment itself highlights the community's strong need, which counterbalances the positive aspects developed through the investment. The result is the City's having almost no impact on neighborhood image.

5.4.2.4 Neighborhood Management

The City's efforts at helping neighborhoods manage themselves are minimal and largely ineffective. The City includes only the bare minimum required public participation in receiving feedback about proposed projects. The City does little to connect neighborhood residents with others outside their community and does not promote the involvement of local institutions (MacDonald 2006). The City also does not promote participation in decision making or encourage neighborhoods to compete for

funding or other resources. In summary, the City's community development efforts do not have a significant impact on neighborhood community development.

5.4.3 Conclusion

The City, with the help of federal funding, has a large impact on the physical conditions of local neighborhoods. In addition, the City acts in many communities as a stabilizing force for both local commercial and residential real estate markets. However, as the model suggests, the local government in Cincinnati is unsuccessful at improving neighborhood image or the ability of neighborhoods to manage themselves. Although the local government in Cincinnati is often criticized, its results are typical of most local governments across the country. Local government's main role is in funding and in most cases this translates to physical improvements, which allow local government officials and politicians to point to concrete results. It is difficult for local governments to claim success in initiatives designed to improve neighborhood image or management and for this reason they often do not invest money in these areas.

5.5 Business Leadership Coalitions - Cincinnati Center City Development Corporation

The Cincinnati Center City Development Corporation (3CDC) is one of two major private, corporate community development efforts in Cincinnati. The organization has been in existence for only two-and-a-half years but already has had a major impact on the communities on which it focuses. 3CDC is a classic example of a Business Leadership Coalition's community development efforts.

5.5.1 History and Structure

5.5.1.1 Neighborhood Background

As its name implies, 3CDC's mission is to focus on development in the center city. This includes both the Central Business District (CBD) and the adjacent Over the Rhine neighborhood. These two neighborhoods will be discussed separately due to the vast differences between them. The CBD, although clean and relatively safe, was in a slight decline at the time 3CDC was formed. The CBD was suffering from the usual decline in manufacturing that was affecting the entire Midwest during the latter part of the 20th century, the more recent economic downturn in the national economy, continued flight to new suburbs developing further and further from the City, and the fallout from a period of racial unrest in early 2001. Both economic conditions and the City's poor image worked together to slow development and investment in the City's core. Little or no new development or redevelopment was taking place. The City's infrastructure was in average shape and residents of the larger metropolitan area generally had negative views of the City's downtown.

Over the Rhine suffered many of the same problems as the CBD but to a much greater degree. Over the Rhine is widely regarded as the City's worst neighborhood and at the time 3CDC was formed Over the Rhine was a hotbed of criminal activity. The neighborhood led the city in violent crimes, murders, and drug activity in the last part of the decade (MacDonald 2006). The infrastructure of the neighborhood was crumbling, along with its housing stock. Over the Rhine boasts the nation's largest collection of intact Italianate architecture yet by 2000 the majority of the Over the Rhine's buildings

were abandoned and decaying (Bracey 2006). In addition, the neighborhood that had once sustained a population of nearly 80,000 had seen its population drop to under 6,000. In addition, years of infighting, particularly between social service providers and groups wishing to preserve the historic neighborhood, had crippled the neighborhood's ability to affect its own future (MacDonald 2006). In summary, Over the Rhine was a desperate community in need of effective community development efforts. Together, Over the Rhine and the CBD were far from being considered neighborhoods of choice.

5.5.1.2 Organizational History

3CDC is a private non-profit corporation formed by the City of Cincinnati to spearhead development downtown and in Over the Rhine. 3CDC was formed as a result of the recommendation of an economic development task force formed by Mayor Charlie Luken at the beginning of his last term as Mayor. The task force recommended that a private, non-profit development corporation be formed to bring in professional expertise in order to spur development and, in the process, avoid the red tape and political maneuvering that can hinder government community development efforts. The Mayor then approached local business leaders with the idea and several provided start-up funding for the organization in early 2003.

5.5.1.3 Structure

Although 3CDC was created at the request of the Mayor and often works in close concert with City officials, especially the City's Economic Development Director, the organization is wholly private. The driving force behind 3CDC is the city's business

community. 3CDC is governed by a board of directors composed mainly of local business leaders, whose companies provide the funding for its operation. This handful of business leaders and the organization's CEO hold all of the power for decision making. The majority of 3CDC's work is focused on two main projects, the redevelopment of Over-the-Rhine and the revitalization of Fountain Square, in the heart of the CBD.

3CDC and its staff are also responsible for managing the Cincinnati Equity Fund (CEF) and the Cincinnati New Markets Fund (CNMF), which pool money from various investors to serve as the primary funding mechanisms for the projects the organization undertakes (as well as various other downtown development projects). CEF was established in 1997 as the result of a collaborative private effort that raised \$45.9 million to provide gap financing in center city projects. The private sector created the Cincinnati New Market Fund, LLC in 2004 by utilizing the federal New Markets Tax Credit program, and raised \$50 million in private capital to assist in funding Center City projects, which was matched by \$50 million in federal tax credits offered to the investors as a result of their contribution to the Fund as part of the New Markets Tax Credit program. In addition, the City of Cincinnati has committed to invest \$100 million over five years to support center city projects. These funds come primarily from Downtown and Over the Rhine Tax Increment Financing (TIF) districts.

Figure 4: 3CDC Organizational Chart

Source: Author 2006

These funds are key to the organization as they provide a reliable source of millions of dollars to support 3CDC development efforts. The organization is able to undertake all these various responsibilities with an extremely small staff of only nine full-time employees (including three administrative assistants) and two part-time interns. The staff members have significant real estate and development experience both in the public and private sectors. The small staff is divided evenly between the corporation’s two main projects, the Fountain Square revitalization project and the redevelopment of Over-the-Rhine (see Figure 4), with the President and CEO overseeing both projects.

5.5.2 Outcomes

The Cincinnati Center City Development Corporation’s structure is typical of most BLCs engaged in community development. 3CDC is driven by local corporate

leaders, takes on large real estate redevelopment projects, and receives funding assistance from the local government. For these reasons, 3CDC's results also reflect that of a typical BLC.

5.5.2.1 Physical Conditions

3CDC has had a major impact on physical conditions in the neighborhoods on which it concentrates. The \$42 million renovation of Fountain Square and the public parking garage below is nearing completion and the \$78 million in improvements to the surrounding properties also have begun. The end result will be a significant physical transformation of the downtown core, dramatically improving both the building stock and infrastructure of the area. Similarly, 3CDC has begun to have an important affect on the physical condition of Over the Rhine. The organization has purchased over 80 vacant or dilapidated buildings and more than 20 vacant lots in the neighborhood. The properties have been cleaned and secured systematically, making the neighborhood a safer place by limiting the areas available for illegal activity (Jones 2006).

The cleanup of these often hazardous properties has had a notable environmental impact as well. In addition, the renovation of 14 buildings, which will become 48 market rate and affordable condominiums and 12 rental units, has begun and will be complete within one year. All of these improvements to the physical conditions of both the CBD and Over the Rhine were made possible by the staff's real estate and development expertise. Each of the projects required complicated financing plans and significant management follow-through. The expertise of the staff and the independent nature of the organization, and the financial backing of the corporate community- conditions that exist

in organizations falling under the BLC model- have enabled 3CDC to be successful in undertaking extremely large projects to improve the physical conditions of the neighborhoods.

5.5.2.2 Market Conditions

In addition to improving the physical conditions of the neighborhood significantly, 3CDC has been able to have a profound effect on local real estate markets. The \$78 million in investments by property owners surrounding the Fountain Square project has created a significant addition to the market for available commercial space. The renovated commercial spaces have been successful in attracting new retail and restaurant activity to a previously declining CBD (Boorne 2006). 3CDC's work in Over the Rhine has had a similar effect on residential real estate markets there. The organization has spent over \$8 million to buy over 60% of the buildings in its area of focus around Washington Park. While this initial investment dwarfs almost every CDC or CCI organization's largest projects, it represents just the initial phase of 3CDC's work in Over the Rhine. The funding available to 3CDC and the development experience of its staff have been key to its ability successfully to impact local commercial and residential real estate markets. Like most BLCs, 3CDC is capable of undertaking projects on a large enough scale so that they can have fundamental impacts on local real estate markets.

5.5.2.3 Image

3CDC has not had a strong impact on the image of either of the neighborhoods in which it is active. Although the organization has attempted to create enthusiasm for the

renovation of Fountain Square, the organization's small size and lack of skill and experience in this area have led to little success in this area of work. Likewise, 3CDC's involvement as a private developer in Over the Rhine has caused public debate rather than strong support from the community or the public at large. Over the Rhine has long been immersed in a struggle for power between local institutions and 3CDC has only served to make that struggle more visible. To date, 3CDC has not been successful at impacting neighborhood image in the CBD or Over the Rhine. However, time will tell whether or not the completion of the development projects will begin to improve either neighborhood's image.

5.5.2.4 Neighborhood Management

3CDC has not made a strong contribution to neighborhood management. As mentioned earlier, 3CDC had contributed to, rather than helped to ease, conflict between local institutions. Although 3CDC has held public information sessions, the organization has not engaged the public in any decision making and has provided no opportunities to create linkages with or among local residents. 3CDC has brought resources to the neighborhoods in which it works, but many of those resources were already earmarked for use in those communities and 3CDC was simply the vehicle for the distribution of those resources. In other words, 3CDC has effectively utilized funds already targeted for the communities rather than obtaining new sources of funding. The organization has made little or no contribution in the area of neighborhood management.

5.5.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, due to its significant funding sources and development experience and expertise, 3CDC has been very effective at improving both the physical and market conditions within the neighborhoods it targets. In fact, in a few short years 3CDC has had a significantly larger impact in these areas than even the most established CDCs and CCIs. However, the organization has made little contribution to date towards improving neighborhood image and has been ineffective at impacting neighborhood management. In fact, 3CDC is attempting essentially to create new neighborhoods rather than improve conditions for those in the community. As discussed in the typology, this is typical of BLCs. The majority of BLCs, including 3CDC, work based on the objectives of leaders from outside the community and largely ignore the concerns and input of those inside the community. However, this is not to suggest, as some have, that the model is flawed. On the contrary, the model is extremely effective at reaching the goals it sets and this may be effective in some communities. The extreme difference in effectiveness across the evaluation framework highlights the need for the typology and the critical evaluation of the models. 3CDC and other BLCs have a place in community development; however there must be proper balance across all areas of the evaluation framework for a neighborhood truly to become a neighborhood of choice.

CHAPTER 6: Findings

6.1 Introduction to Findings

Examination of each of these models makes several things clear. First, each of the models can be effective in one or more areas but no single model is able to have a strong impact across all areas. Second, each of the approaches is effective in different ways and therefore can be uniquely suited for different situations. Some differences between models are great and some are smaller and more subtle. These differences in areas of effectiveness make it important to understand how these models compare to one another and how they fit into the overall framework of neighborhood-level community development. Although more research is needed to understand fully how each model fits into particular neighborhood situations, this research provides the first step to doing so by illuminating these differences between models and showing how the models relate to one another in terms of their areas of effectiveness.

The typology and related illustrative examples provide a foundation from which to compare the models. Here again, the neighborhood of choice evaluation framework serves as a useful guide for doing so. Using this framework, the various models can be compared to one another with respect to how effective they are at each of the four main components of the neighborhoods of choice framework. By comparing how effective each model is in relation to each component of the framework, an overall understanding of each model's role within community development begins to become clear.

6.2 Evaluation of Models Performance

6.2.1 Physical Conditions

The models show wide discrepancy with respect to their effectiveness at impacting the physical conditions of a community. Business Leadership Coalitions have the strongest impact due to the money, power, and influence of the members of the board of directors of the typical BLC, which allow them to attract the capital and expertise necessary to undertake projects that often dwarf those of other models both in size and impact. However, local government, which often plays a role in BLC projects, also has significant funding which it uses primarily to impact physical conditions. Yet, local governments often lack the expertise and political will to undertake projects that have the kind of sweeping impact of some BLC projects. Community development corporations are similar to BLCs, but operate on a much smaller scale. Nonetheless, they can have a significant impact on the physical conditions of a neighborhood through targeted projects that address community needs.

On the other hand, comprehensive community initiatives and community organizing are less effective in this area. CCIs can have a significant impact on conditions of a neighborhood but that impact depends on their area of focus, which in the majority of cases is not physical development. Community organizing is the least suited for impacting physical conditions. Some community organizing efforts do undertake physical improvements but they often lack the capital and expertise to have a significant impact on a neighborhood.

6.2.2 Market Conditions

Physical conditions and market conditions are related in many ways and this fact is apparent when comparing the models' performance in these two areas. However, market conditions and physical conditions should not be confused. Physical improvements do not always translate directly into improvement in real estate market values. Nonetheless, the general comparison of the models in these two areas is very similar. BLCs also have the largest potential to impact market conditions, again because the scale of their projects is generally much larger than the other models'. However, it should be noted that BLCs' projects can be so large that they could have a detrimental effect by introducing too much supply into the market. Nevertheless, this is rarely the case and BLCs have the most potential to impact both commercial and residential real estate markets. In a slight contrast to their effect on physical conditions, CDCs can have a strong impact on local markets. The targeted nature of the projects they engage in and the expertise of their staffs allows CDCs to have impacts greater than would be suggested by their limited size. CDCs their use intimate knowledge of the neighborhood's strengths and weaknesses to use their limited resources to maximum effect.

Unlike CDCs, local government is generally less effective at influencing market conditions than it is at impacting physical conditions. Government sponsored projects often are influenced by outside factors, such as political considerations, which do not allow them to have the targeted impact of CDC ventures. In addition, too much government intervention can be a turn-off to many involved in the real estate market. As a result of these factors, local government typically does not have a strong impact on neighborhood level market conditions. CCIs could have a significant impact in this area,

again depending on their focus, but the majority are not concentrated in this area and therefore have a minimal impact. And finally, the community organizing model's limitations, based on size, lack of expertise and low levels of capital, hinder it from having an impact in this area beyond general neighborhood improvements which may make the neighborhood more appealing.

6.2.3 Image

The models' performance in impacting neighborhood image stands in sharp contrast to their performances regarding physical and market conditions. A large, well managed community organizing effort has the strongest ability to impact neighborhood image both internally and externally. The sheer number of people involved in a community organizing effort allows it to have a forceful impact on internal neighborhood image by positively affecting each individual involved. In addition, the number of people involved often attracts local media attention that improves external opinions of the community. Although they typically do not involve people in the same manner as the community organizing model, CCIs' size and diverse programs allow them to reach a large number of individuals and in the process impact their view of the neighborhood. In addition, both community organizing efforts and CCIs are most likely to undertake activities directly aimed at improving neighborhood image.

While community organizing and CCIs have the greatest impact on both internal and external image, BLCs have the ability to have an immense impact on neighborhood image, but this impact is limited to external views of the community. Unlike community organizing and CCIs, BLCs do not involve community members and in the process can

sometimes lower residents' opinions of their neighborhood. These forces tend to split BLCs impact between internal and external image improvement.

The remaining two models can have positive effects but their impact is frequently very small. CDCs do not engage local citizens and their projects are typically on a small scale that, while having important impacts, may go unnoticed by the casual observer. Government efforts typically attract more attention but are often not projects that affect individuals' opinions of the community. For these reasons CDC and governments efforts typically do not strongly impact neighborhood image.

6.2.4 Neighborhood Management

The models' performance at enhancing neighborhood management is somewhat similar to their impact on neighborhood image. However, there are some important differences that need to be addressed. To begin with, community organizing is by far the strongest in this area. Although the community organizing model is effective at impacting neighborhood image, it is not significantly better than some of the other models in that area. However, its ability to impact neighborhood management far surpasses the ability of the other models. The structure of community organizing groups mirrors the characteristics of effective neighborhood management. While they are not structured to have as great an impact as community organizing efforts, CCIs too can have a strong impact in this area by integrating a number of programs to bring together individuals from the community and connect them to resources both internal and external to the community.

In sharp contrast to community organizing and CCIs, the remaining models do not concentrate their efforts in this area and therefore have minimal or even negative effects. The work of CDCs is almost exclusively focused on physical and market conditions and this, combined with their small staff size and the limited number of residents involved on a day-to-day basis, results in little ability to impact neighborhood management. Likewise, local government efforts generally ignore neighborhood management concerns, as they are difficult for governments to manage and do not easily contribute to concrete impacts that are important to the political leaders. Finally, BLCs often can work counter to neighborhoods' ability to manage themselves by reshaping neighborhoods with limited input or participation from local residents. The fact that each of these three models focuses on bricks and mortar precludes a strong ability on their part to affect neighborhood management.

Figure 5: Community Development Models' Areas of Effectiveness

Source: Author 2006

6.3 Evaluation of Findings

The findings of this study are contrary to most literature on community development, which tends to examine one model or a small range of related models and then suggest that model (or models) is the most effective. As discussed earlier, in such literature other models are discounted or ignored, frequently without empirical study or evidence to back up such dismissal. The typology laid out in this study makes it apparent that each model is uniquely structured for success in particular areas, but no single model is clearly superior to the others in all areas identified by the evaluation framework. In fact, each model is uniquely able to allow for a range of outcomes across the measures identified by neighborhoods of choice. However, in reality most communities in need of community development face obstacles across all the areas identified by the evaluation framework. For this reason, it is difficult for any single model to 100% successful in impacting a community in all areas.

The illustrative examples provide evidence that suggests the typology identifying the strengths and weaknesses of these models holds true in real world situations. Although small differences existed between the conceptually perfect models described in the typology and the related illustrative examples, the illustrative examples for the most part mirrored the conclusions made regarding each model in the typology. This suggests that although differences clearly exist between individual organizations within each model in regard to history, structure, and effectiveness, there is reason to accept many of the conclusions drawn out in the typology.

Comparing the models across the framework provides some interesting insights. At one end of the spectrum, the community organizing model, with the highest level of

local participation, fares the best in the areas of neighborhood management and image, while struggling to impact physical and market conditions. Conversely, the BLC approach, which is at the opposite end of the typology because it includes little or no involvement of local residents, achieves the opposite results, faring very well in regard to its impact on physical and market conditions while having negative impacts on internal image and neighborhood management. In addition, the models which fall between these extremes in regard to participation generally have more moderate achievements but those achievements are better spread across all four of the areas of evaluation. This suggests that the amount of local participation has a significant impact on the areas in which community development organizations are effective. This is important to understand when adopting a model of community development or analyzing the abilities of existing organizations.

The understanding of each model's strengths and weaknesses provided by the typology can be helpful in a number of ways. In addition to highlighting the important role local participation has in affecting community development outcomes, understanding the limitations of each model can assist those utilizing the models to adjust accordingly. For example, understanding the barriers community organizing efforts face when attempting actions aimed at physical improvements can aid these organizations in addressing obstacles or finding new ways to accomplish their goals. Likewise, BLCs that understand their limitations in regard to neighborhood management can begin to think about partnerships with local organizations or other measures to address this shortcoming, which is otherwise fundamental to the model.

Perhaps most important, this typology allows community development practitioners to think more broadly about what community development means. Ideally, the typology permits community development practitioners to understand and appreciate the positive aspects of each of the models rather than focusing narrowly on the approach they are most familiar with and rejecting others. Doing so allows for more creative solutions to the problems facing communities today. It is clear that the problems facing communities are complex and not easily solved. Therefore, a better understanding of how each model of community development impact communities differently is helpful in identifying new ways to approach community development.

Currently, organizations such as intermediaries attempt to assist various community development efforts in addressing their shortcomings. For example, intermediaries attempt to assist organizations with low capacity for physical improvements, such as community organizing efforts, by supplying them with the expertise and capital they lack. This is the type of partnership that can more fully develop the capacity of community development organizations, beyond the limits imposed by the models themselves. However, the role of intermediaries is relatively small and often limited to a specific area of expertise. More work is needed to bridge the capabilities of the various approaches in order to solve more effectively the multifaceted difficulties facing communities.

6.4 Directions for Future Research

This study is merely the first step toward understanding how different models of community development impact distressed communities. Further research is needed to

determine which model or models are the best fit for a particular neighborhood and how the various models can utilize intermediaries or other forms of partnership to overcome their shortcomings. To begin with, it is not clear whether a neighborhood with strong existing neighborhood management characteristics but lacking in physical and market conditions would benefit from a model such as CDC, which impacts physical and market conditions, or would benefit more from a model such as community organizing which could build on the neighborhood's existing strengths. Likewise, it is unclear which model is the best fit for a community significantly lacking in all four of the areas identified by neighborhoods of choice. A model such as CCI might be most effective because of its relative strength across all areas. However, it easily could be argued that one of the models at the extreme ends of the spectrum might be necessary to address the community's pressing needs. More research is needed to answer these important questions.

In addition, more research needs to be done to highlight the role of intermediaries in assisting community development organizations in overcoming the shortcomings of the models they utilize and to examine if there are opportunities for seemingly opposing models, such as community organizing and BLCs, to partner or work parallel to one another in the same neighborhood. Significant further research is necessary to understand more about how that models fit within specific neighborhood contexts and to examine ways in which opposing models can work with each other or outside organizations to overcome their limitations.

Bibliography

Alinsky, S. 1972. *Rules for Radicals: A practical primer for realistic radicals*. New York, NY: Vintage.

Arnold, Christy. 2005. "Neighborhood erodes in the face of crime, poverty." *The Cincinnati Enquirer*. November 6, 1B.

Austin, J. and A. McCaffery. 2002. "Business Leadership Coalitions and Public-Private partnerships in American Cities: A business perspective on regime theory." *Journal of Urban Affairs*, 24:1, 34-54.

Beauregard, R.A. 1998. "Public-private Partnerships as Historical Chameleons: The case of the United States." In J Pierre, (Ed.), *Partnerships in Urban Governance*. New York, NY: St. Martin Press.

Bowling, C. 2002. "Price Hill Will Appreciative Inquiry Interview Questions". Unpublished.

Brown, P. 1996. "Comprehensive Neighborhood-Based Initiatives." *Cityscape*, 2:2, 161-176.

Bruner, C. 1991. *Thinking Collaboratively: Ten questions and answers to help policy makers improve children's services*. Washington, D.C.: The Aspen Institute.

Chaskin, R.J., M.L. Joseph., and S. Chipenda-Dansoka. 1997. "Implementing Comprehensive Community Development: Possibilities and limitations." *Social Work*, 42:5, 435-444.

City of Cincinnati. 2005. *Department of Community Development and Planning Quarterly Report: Third Quarter 2005*. Cincinnati, OH: City of Cincinnati.

Drier, P. 1996. "Community Empowerment Strategies: The limits and potential of community organizing in urban neighborhoods". *Cityscape: A Journal of Policy Development and Research*, 2, 121-159.

Gans, H. J. 1991. *People, Plans, and Policies*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.

Gittell, R. and A. Vidal. 1998. *Community Organizing: Building Social Capital as a Development Strategy*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Green, G.P. and A. Haines. *Asset Building and Community Development*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

- Halpern, R. 1995. *Rebuilding the Inner City: A history of neighborhood initiatives to address poverty in the United States*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.
- Harvey, D. 1993. "A View From Federal Hill." In F. Fee, L. Shopes, & L. Zeidman, (Eds.), *The Baltimore Book: New views of local history*. Philadelphia, PA: Temple University Press.
- Horwitt, S. 1989. *Let Them Call Me Rebel: The life and Legacy of Saul Alinsky*. New York, NY: Aflred A. Knopf.
- Howard, A. 2003. "Village poised for revitalization." *The Cincinnati Enquirer*. 22 January, B3.
- Jargowski, 1998. *Poverty and Place: Ghettos, barrios and the American city*. New York, NY: Russell Sage Foundation.
- Kanters, A. 2006a. *Summary of Accomplishments*. Lincoln Heights, OH: Lincoln Heights Community Improvement Corporation.
- Keith, N.Z. (1996). "Can urban school reform and community development be joined? The potential of community schools." *Education and Urban Society*, 28:2, 237-268.
- Kemme, S. 2004. "Village devises development plan." *The Cincinnati Enquirer*. 18 February, B1.
- Kretzmann, J.P. and J.L. McKnight. 1993. *Building Communities from the Inside Out: A Path Toward Finding and Mobilizing a Community's Assets*. Evanston, IL: Institute for Policy Research.
- Krumholz, N. 1999. "Equitable Approaches to Local Economic Development." *Policy Studies Journal*, 27:1, 83-95.
- Kubisch, A.C., P. Brown, R. A. Chaskin, J. Hiorta, M. Joseph, H. Richman and M. Roberts. 1997. *Voices From the Field: Learning from comprehensive community initiatives*. Washington, D.C.: The Aspen Institute.
- Lane, B. and D. Dorfman. 1997. *Strengthening Community Networks: The Basis for Sustainable Community Renewal*. Portland, OR: Northwest Regional Education Laboratory. Online at <http://www.nwrel.org/ruraled/strengthening.html#i>. Accessed December 5, 2005.
- Langdon, P. 1994. *A Better Place to Live: Reshaping the American Suburb*. Amherst, MA: University of Massachusetts Press.

Luloff, A.E., and J. Bridger. 2003. "Community Agency and Local Development." In D. Brown and L. Swanson (Eds.) *Challenges for Rural America in the Twenty-First Century*. University Park, PA: Pennsylvania State University Press.

Monk, D. 2005. "Lincoln Heights wins project Nod." *Cincinnati Business Courier*. 2 September, 4.

National Congress for Community Economic Development. 1995. *Tying It All Together: The comprehensive achievements of community-based development organizations*. Washington, DC: Author.

Nedland, M., M. Schubert. 2002. *Creating Neighborhoods of Choice Through Revitalization*. Washington, D.C.: Neighborhood Reinvestment Training Institute.

Osborne, K. 2003. "Cap on housing vouchers rejected". *The Cincinnati Post*. 24 December, 3B.

Peterman, W. 2000. *Neighborhood Planning and Community Based Development*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Pierce, M. 2006. "Price Hill's will: A neighborhood summons its talents to remake itself". *CityBeat*. January 4. Online at www.citybeat.com/2006-01-04/news.shtml. Accessed 27 January 2006.

Price Hill Will. 2005. *Who We Are*. Online at www.pricehillwill.org/whoweare.htm. Accessed 27 January 2006.

Putnam, R. 1995. "Bowling Alone: America's declining social capital." *Journal of Democracy* 6:1, 65-78.

Ross, B.H. and M.A. Levine. 1996. *Urban Politics: Power in metropolitan America*. Itasca, IL: Peacock.

Rubin, J.S. and Stankiewicz, G.M. 2001. "The Los Angeles Community Development Bank: The possible pitfalls of public-private Partnerships." *Journal of Urban Affairs*, 23:2, 133-153.

Southworth, M. and E. Ben-Joseph. 1995. "Street Standards and the Shaping of Suburbia." *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 61, 65-81.

Smock, K. 2004. *Democracy in Action: Community organizing and urban change*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.

Stoecker, R. 2001. *Community Development and Community Organizing: Apples to oranges? Chicken and Egg?*. Online at www.yepp-community.org/downloads/empowerment/Community%20Development%20Stoecker.pdf. Accessed 3 February 2006.

Summers, G. 1986. "Rural Community Development." *Annual Review of Sociology*. 12:341-371.

Temkin, K. and W. Rohe. 1997. "Social Capital and Neighborhood Stability: An empirical investigation." *Housing Policy Debate*, 9(1), 23-41.

Thomas, J.M. and J.E. Grigsby III. "Community Development". In C.J. Hoch, L.C. Dalton, and F.S. So (Eds.) *The Practice of Local Government Planning*. Washington, D.C.: International City/County Management Association.

Turner, M., Popkin, S., and Cunningham, M. 2000. Section 8 Mobility and Neighborhood Health. Washington, DC: Urban Institute.

Twelvetrees, A. C. 1996. *Organizing for Neighborhood Development: A Comparative Study of Community Based Development Organizations*. Brookfield, VT: Ashgate Publishing Company.

Walker, C. 1993. "Nonprofit Housing Development: Status, trends, and prospects." *Housing Policy Debate*, 4(3), 369-414.

Wilkinson, K. 1991. *The Community in Rural America*. New York, NY: Greenwood Press.

Interviews

Boorne, M. L. 2006. Interview by author. 3 April.

Bracey, D. 2006. Interview by author. 5 April.

Frye, T. 2006. Interview by author. 31 March.

Holmes, B. Interview by author. 23 April.

Kanters, A. 2006. Interview by author. 17 April.

MacDonald, D. 2006. Interview by author. 4 April.

Munitz, C. 2006. Interview by author. 7 April.

Musser, H.A. 2006. Interview by author. 23 January.

Pugh, J. 2006. Interview by author. 6 March.

Witte, P. 2006. Interview by author. 26 January.

Woods, K. 2006. Interview by author. 6 March.